

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

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Risk Assessment Report

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1 HAZARD CHARACTERIZATION

1.1 Scope

This report addresses identification of hazards related to leakage from the storage site. The report is based on guidance in the EU CCS Directive 2009-31-EC (European Parliament, Council of the European Union , 2009),and as such concerns the following:

- Potential leakage pathways
- Potential magnitude of leakage events for identified leakage pathways (flux rates)
- Critical parameters affecting potential leakage
- Secondary effects of storage of CO₂
- Other factors which could pose a hazard to human health or the environment

The first three items above are considered mainly part of hazard characterization, while the latter two items, as well as exposure and effects assessment and finally overall risk characterization, is the subject of risk analysis and subsequently risk evaluation.

The assessments in this report are based on a combination of site-specific information, relevant models, analyses from related work packages of the project, and judgments to the best of our knowledge.

The simulations performed to obtain estimates of potential leakage magnitudes for different are dependent on a large number of parameters, many of which are associated with a large degree of uncertainty. The approach taken here is to quantify these uncertainties and propagate them onto the results. It must however be appreciated that the quality of the results are proportional to the available knowledge, assumptions and limitations of quantified parameters and dependent models. Assumptions of both current and future states of a given system will likely never be an exact reflection of reality. Thus, values presented in this report should never be used and interpreted beyond the context in which they were originally created.

1.2 Context

CO₂-SPICER Work Package 6 covers the main steps of a risk assessment process, conforming to the ISO 31000:2018 standard. Risk (or hazard) identification, is the first phase (Task 6.1), providing the foundation for the proceeding risk analysis (Tasks 6.2 & 6.3) and risk evaluation (Task 6.4). The framework is shown in Fig. 1-1.

Fig. 1-1: The main steps of a generic risk assessment framework (ISO, 2018).

The risk identification serves the purpose of screening the most important risks through collection of relevant data and preliminary assessments and provides the foundation for the subsequent activities. In the following risk analysis, the most important risks are further analyzed, especially with respect to exposure and effects. Finally, the risk evaluation (characterization) compares the analyzed risks with relevant criteria to judge the acceptability, and to provide input to the decision-making process.

1.3 Area of interest

Chapter 1.3 is directly based on CO₂-SPICER report R1.2 (Janderková, Sedláček, & Krejčí, 2022), and further details can be found there. Here a brief overview of the area of interest is provided. The main conclusion of report R1.2 is that *“the collected data do not indicate any substantial limitations on the use of the Zar-3 site for geological storage of carbon dioxide within the meaning of the [Czech Act No. 85/2012 Sb].”*. (Janderková, Sedláček, & Krejčí, 2022).

This risk assessment is limited to address risks stemming from or impacting on the area shown in Fig. 1-2 bounded by the black rectangle (“Area of 3D seismic and geological structural mapping”); this is throughout this report referred to as “area of interest” or “main area of interest”. The term “wider area of interest” represents the entire map portion shown in Fig. 1-2.

1.3.1 Basic information

The area of interest, representing the surroundings of the structure referred to as “Zar-3” (Žarošice hydrocarbon field), is located in the southeastern part of the Czech Republic. The wider area of interest encompasses 94.5 km². A structural geology mapping project (inner area

of interest, 3D seismic area) defined a smaller polygon with an area of 15 km² inside of the wider area of interest. The Zar-3 structure is located in the center of the inner area of interest.

The area of interest is located in the South Moravian Region and, to a greater or lesser extent, spans three administrative districts. Fig. 1-2 shows the administrative division of the area of interest.

Fig. 1-2: Area demarcation and administrative division.

The largest part of the wider area of interest belongs to the Hodonín district and falls under the administrative district of the municipality with extended powers (ORP) of Kyjov. The northern part belongs to the Vyškov district and to the administrative districts of the Slavkov u Brna and Bučovice ORPs, and only a very small part in the area's southeastern part belongs to the Břeclav district and the administrative district of the Hustopeče ORP. The wider area of interest extends into several cadastral areas: Archlebov, Bohumilice, Dambořice, Dražůvky, Heršpice, Koberčice u Brna, Lovčice u Kyjova, Mouřínov, Násedlovice, Stavěšice, Strážovice, Uhřice u Kyjova, Velké Hostěrádky, Věteřov, Žarošice, Ždánice, Želetice u Kyjova (in

alphabetical order). The inner area of interest is located in the cadastral areas of Archlebov, Uhřice, Žarošice and Ždánice.

1.3.2 Surface water

The greater part of the area of interest belongs to the Dyje River Basin and only a small northwestern part to the Svratka River Basin. The drainage divide between the Svratka and Dyje river basins runs along the ridge of the Ždánický les Highland.

There are water reservoirs on some watercourses in the area of interest. The more important ones include the Nový Pond on Milešovický Creek (1.5 ha), Klášov Pond on Klášovský Creek (0.5 ha), Panské Ponds (1.25 ha) and Horní and Dolní Dražůvky ponds (0.7 and 0.9 ha) on the Trkmanka River, and particularly the Balaton Pond (3.6 ha) on Spálený Stream.

1.3.3 Groundwater

With regard to groundwater used as a source of drinking water, most of the territory is classified in the category QC II “Groundwater requiring complicated treatment for drinking water supply“, and western part of the area is even classified in the category of QC III “Groundwater nearly or completely unsuitable for drinking water supply“. Groundwater classified as QC I “Groundwater suitable for drinking water supply” occurs only in the northeastern part of the wider area of interest, on the northern slopes of the Ždánický les Highland.

1.3.4 Nature and landscape protection

Currently, no extensive specially protected area occurs in the area of interest. However, several small special protection areas have been declared in the territory of the Ždánický les Highland Nature Park. The Ochozy Natural Monument (ÚSOP registration code 2203, IUCN Category IV - Habitat/Species Management Area) lies directly in the area of interest.

Natural monuments are defined as smaller natural formations, geological or geomorphological formations and occurrences of minerals or rare or endangered species in habitat fragments. The Ochozy Natural Monument has a total area of 0.95 ha and lies in the cadastral area of Archlebov, on the right valley slope of Spálený Stream, at an elevation of 274 to 319 m above sea level. It consists of species-rich thermophilous grasslands on the southern slope of the Ždánický les Highland with occurrences of protected plant and animal species.

The subject of protection is the preservation of critically endangered species such as the bee orchid (*Ophrys apifera*), the highly endangered military orchid (*Orchis militaris*) and many other endangered species such as the white helleborine (*Cephalanthera damasonium*), fragrant orchid (*Gymnadenia conopsea*), star gentian (*Gentiana cruciata*) and so forth. A number of thermophilous insect species are also associated with the occurring vegetation.

1.3.5 Plants and animals' protection

Occurrence sites of specially protected plant and animal species of national significance (abbreviated as nationally significant species) are located in the area of interest particularly in the territory of the Ždánický les Highland. The species include the narrow-lipped helleborine (*Epipactis leptochila*) at two sites in the cadastral area of Koberčice, hairy flax (*Linum hirsutum*)

subsp. hirsutum) at two sites in the cadastral areas of Archlebov and Ždánice, and Alcon blue (Phengaris alcon) at one site in the cadastral area of Archlebov.

The Ždánický les Highland is also the core area of a biotope of selected specially protected large mammal species. The biotope relates to the following selected species of large mammals:

grey wolf, Eurasian lynx, brown bear and elk. All these species have specific requirements and their life strategy involves long-distance migration, which is essential for their survival in our territory. Migration corridors are an integral part of the biotopes of selected specially protected large mammal species.

1.3.6 Population

A total of seven villages and the town of Ždánice are located in the wider area of interest. Dambořice and Žarošice are larger villages with good civic facilities. Násedlovice and Želetice extend only partly into the area of interest, and the other villages lie within the defined wider area. In 2022, roughly 8,300 inhabitants lived in the wider area of interest: 1,100 in Žarošice and 871 in Archlebov (the two villages partially inside the main area of interest).

1.3.7 Transport and infrastructure

A major thoroughfare of the area of interest is the first-class road I/54 Slavkov u Brna – Žarošice – Kyjov – Veselí nad Moravou – Strání/Moravské Liesková border crossing. It is connected with the following second-class roads: II/431 Ždánice – Bučovice – Vyškov, II/419 Žarošice – Čejč, II/381 Žarošice – Velké Hostěrádky – Velké Němčice – Pohořelice. The region's road network also includes third-class and local roads. Road I/54 passes through the urban area of the villages of Žarošice and Archlebov.

Drinking water is distributed to the communities by a main or local water supply network, and some residents also use water from their own wells. Six communities are currently connected to or have their own wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). The village of Archlebov plans to build its own WWTP.

The Klobouky – Loukov gasoline pipeline (ČEPRO a.s.) with a protected zone of 300 m on both sides from the pipeline axis (Act No. 161/2013 Sb., Government Regulation No. 29/1959 Sb.) passes through the southeastern part of the wider area of interest. The V280 Sokolnice – Senica cross-border high voltage power line to Slovakia with a voltage of 220 kV and a domestic power line with a voltage of 110 kV pass through the southern half of the wider area of interest. Both lines have a protected zone of 15 m delimited by vertical planes on both sides of the line, measured perpendicularly to the line from the outer conductor (Act No. 458/2000 Sb.).

1.4 Preliminary risk screening

An early screening process was conducted to identify risk sources, preventive and mitigating barriers, possible consequences, and other factors of relevance. The objective was to use this as a basis for then determining which leakage scenarios were relevant for the Zar-3 field and this project. These findings, based on an FEP (Features, Events, Processes) analysis are briefly listed in table. The selected leakage scenarios are then listed in Chapter 1.5.

Tab. 1-1: FEP analysis results for screening of risks

Category	Considered items
Risk sources	Sabotage/intentional threats Injection pressure/temperature/volume CO2 impurities Wellbore design/barrier weaknesses Displaced hydrocarbons/metals/other Caprock weaknesses/limitations Faults/fractures (existing or induced)
Leakage causes	Well: Cement plug defects (cracks/microannuli) Well: Annular cement defects (cracks/microannuli) Caprock: Geomechanical degradation due to cooling/re-pressurization Caprock: Existing defects Fault/fracture: reactivation due to pressure Spill point: Exceeding storage capacity
Preventive barriers	Wellbore seals (plugs, annular cement, other) Casings Caprock/Overburden Sealing faults
Mitigating barriers (measures)	Seismic data monitoring Soil gas analysis Pressure/temperature adjustments Injection rate adjustments Relocation of injection wells Monitoring wells Re-abandonment
Consequences (possible targets at risk)	Humans in proximity areas Residential areas Industrial areas Infrastructure Soils/sediments Flora/fauna (plants, animals) Surface water Groundwater Atmosphere
Considerations/Concerns	Uncertainties Available information Timescale of leakage Stakeholders Regulations (current and future) Changes in land use Meteorology

1.5 Leakage scenarios

The following leakage scenarios have been considered from a storage integrity point of view:

- Leakage from abandoned wellbores (Chapter 1.6)
- Leakage through caprock (Chapter 1.7)
- Leakage through faults/fractures (Chapter 1.8)
- Leakage from spill point (Chapter 1.9)
- Leakage from injection or monitoring well (Chapter 1.10)

Leakage from abandoned wellbores is considered the most important scenario (in terms of both likelihood and consequence) and is therefore given considerably more attention than all other scenarios with respect to quantitative assessments. Leakage through caprock is assessed in terms of both geomechanical stability analysis and simplistic assessments of possible leakage rates, while faults and spill points are considered mainly qualitatively based on available data. To the extent possible, uncertainties has been attempted quantified.

Leakage scenarios listed above constitute the scope of assessed scenarios; other scenarios not listed are therefore considered of lesser relevance with respect to either likelihood of occurrence, impact, or both, in a storage integrity perspective.

CO₂ is considered the main focus in relation to leaking gas. Risks to human health and safety arise (almost) exclusively from elevated CO₂ concentrations in ambient air, either in confined outdoor environments, in caves or in buildings (IPCC, 2005). However, to the extent possible, leakage of hydrocarbon gas has also been considered for the defined leakage scenarios. For the purpose of simplicity, hydrocarbon gas has in this context been equated to CH₄ (methane). Methane is a component of natural gas, mainly used as a fuel source and chemical feedstock in industries. It is usually harmless, however, at high concentrations, it may reduce the oxygen percentage in air, acting as an asphyxiant. It is also extremely flammable and can cause an explosion when its concentration reaches 5% to 15% in air¹.

The primary focus of this report is long-term storage risks post-injection. However, the main risk in an injection/monitoring perspective has also been assessed, which is a loss of well control (blowout) event from an injection/monitoring well and subsequent release of hydrocarbons and/or CO₂. This is discussed in Chapter 1.10.

1.6 Leakage from abandoned wellbores

Leakage through wells is a primary concern given the potential flow rates to surface that might occur through such a large direct connection from the reservoir to the surface. There are in this context three types of wells that may leak: injection wells from which the CO₂ is injected during the injection phase of the field, monitoring wells used to monitor the behavior of the reservoir while the CO₂ is injected and for a time period after the injection phase, and abandoned wells which include both of the other two well types after their active phase as well as all previously drilled wells in the field. This chapter focuses on leakage from abandoned wellbores, which is the scenario most relevant from a long-term storage integrity perspective.

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3617131/>

1.6.1 Wells in area of interest

The area of interest and its surrounding area contains multiple wells, including both wells currently in operation, wellbores recently abandoned, and wellbores originally abandoned decades ago. The locations of these wells are shown in the map below.

Fig. 1-3: Locations of wellbores for area of interest (blue region) and surrounding area. Only wellbores within area of interest are considered in this report.

This report only considers leakage from those wellbores within the defined area of interest, i.e. the blue region of Fig. 1-3. The coordinates for this region is shown in table Tab. 1-2.

Tab. 1-2: Coordinates for area of interest (confining limits for wells considered in this report)

Northing WGS84	Easting WGS84
49.025824	16.969555
49.045288	16.941172
49.076379	16.990581
49.056894	17.018961

The wellbores located within this area, and their location, is provided in Tab. 1-3.

Tab. 1-3: Wells included within area of interest

Well	Abandonment year	Coordinates (WGS84)	
		Northing	Easting
UH3	1978	49,05062	16,9811
UH5	1978	49,05102	17,00433
UH6	1983	49,06563	16,99659
UH9	1997	49,04054	16,94878
UH10	2003	49,03391	16,95923
UH11	1981	49,05828	16,96697
UH12	1980	49,06926	16,99186
UH16	1991	49,04643	16,95545
ZA1	1968	49,05046	16,96212
ZA3	well in operation	49,05036	16,97106
ZA4	unusable section abandoned	49,05051	16,97101
ZA4A	well in operation	49,05051	16,97101
ZA5H	well in operation	49,05582	16,96912
ZA6	unusable section abandoned	49,0557	16,96916
ZA6A	well in operation	49,0557	16,96916
ZA7	well in operation	49,0503	16,97109
ZA8H	unusable section abandoned	49,05558	16,96874
ZA8AH	well in operation	49,05558	16,96874
ZA9H	unusable section abandoned	49,05022	16,97111
ZA9AH	well in operation	49,05022	16,97111
ZA12	2018	49,0556	16,9689
ZA14H	well in operation	49,05017	16,97113

The wells listed are all planned for re-abandonment prior to any CO₂ injection.

For leakage simulation purposes, only wells that are drilled into reservoir formations are considered further. The reason for this is that the simulation framework assumes a direct contact point from where the leaking gas is originally located and the well it subsequently flows into.

Of the wells listed in Tab. 1-3, wells UH5, UH6, UH12 and ZA9H do not expose reservoir formations, and have thus not been simulated.

1.6.2 Leakage simulation framework

A framework for quantitatively assessing leakage rates for plugged and abandoned wells is briefly presented here. For further details, please refer to (Moeinikia, et al., 2018) and the references therein. The main input parameters consist of deterministic input, such as well and P&A design and reservoir characteristics, as well as uncertain inputs that typically relate to the size of fractures, micro-annuli and permeability of cement. Assuming that the uncertain input parameters can somehow be established, the underlying models for leakage rates (bulk, fractures, micro-annuli) are run in a Monte Carlo framework to produce leakage rate distributions. In the model outcomes, as the storage complex pressures evolve over time, so too does the resulting leakage rate. In this framework, parameter uncertainties are represented as probability distributions.

Fig. 1-4: Simulation framework for leakage from abandoned wells.

The framework is obviously strongly dependent on the quality of assumed input parameters. There is also an intrinsic assumption that the current and future states of the wellbore is either known or can be inferred from well-specific information (which may or may not exist). Moreover, the flow model is based on Darcy flow, and as such the assumed prevailing pressure in the wellbore (or factors impacting pressure) will have a substantial impact on leakage rates. Also crucial to flow potential are microannuli gap size, viscosity of fluid and length of cement barriers.

The underlying models are not explained in depth here but a brief description of their purpose in the model framework is provided here. PVT models are used to established basic fluid properties, such as density and viscosity. These models use black oil, hydrocarbon gas or CO₂ correlations. The material balance model links reservoir pressure change with formation pore volume, fluid volumes, produced volumes, aquifer influx and injected volumes, such that predictions of future reservoir pressure can be made. Stress model relates changes in reservoir pressure with changes in the stress plane around the wellbore, which is considered here. Failure mode and microannuli models determine which type of failure will occur and specific

parameters of each failure mode, while leakage rate model transforms the barrier defect and fluid properties to a leakage rate. Time-to-failure model uses Bayesian analysis of lifetime data to predict mean time to failure, but is not considered here due to a lack of relevant statistical data. Finally, the Monte Carlo simulation framework provides uncertainty propagation by repeatedly running simulations with sampled values from stochastic input parameters.

In the following sections, the main assumptions and limitations, and the input parameters used in the simulation framework for leakage from abandoned wellbores in this report, is provided.

1.6.3 Leakage pathways: Assumptions and limitations

There are in theory an unlimited number of unique migration pathways, and the framework does not attempt to capture even the majority of these. Each well has been assessed based on assuming one possible migration pathway, which breaches the minimum number of well barrier elements (cement plugs or cemented annular sections) required to exit to the surface environment. Migration pathways here are therefore limited to those inside the wellbore. Pathways on the outside of the wellbore are not considered. There are however no indications that such migration pathways should yield higher leakage rates than those considered inside the wellbore. As such, the considered migration pathways should represent, in terms of leakage magnitude, also excluded pathways.

Bypassing cemented barriers could occur due to various reasons, such as general migration through porous bulk medium, through cracks in the cement or through microannuli in e.g. cement/casing steel interfaces. In the simulations, only microannuli have been considered. The reasoning for this is that it represents the more likely pathway, and also that the leakage potential is more significant in this case.

Fig. 1-5: Possible leakage pathways through an abandoned well (Gasda, Bachu, & Celia, 2004).

Aside from pressure, the framework is also strongly dependent on the size of the flow channels where fluid or gas migrates upwards. The size of such channels is difficult to determine, as no information exists on the future state of cemented well barriers. There are however published studies that indicate likely ranges, see e.g. Fig. 1-6 (based on (Stormont, Fernandez, Taha, & Matteo, 2018) or (Aas, et al., 2016), and which could be used in lack of better information.

Fig. 1-6: Hydraulic aperture of microannulus as a function of effective wellbore permeability (Stormont, Fernandez, Taha, & Matteo, 2018).

In the leakage simulations presented in this report, microannuli aperture ranges have been established based on the experiments presented in (Aas, et al., 2016). A general microannuli gap size of T(3, 20, 70) µm is used throughout. This assumption has been made for lack of well-specific information pertaining to the existing state of cemented well barriers for the wells in the area of interest. The implication is that difference in simulated potential leakage rates is not the result of relatively better or worse conditions of any one well barrier compared to another; they are considered to be of the same quality. Rather, the difference is mainly due to either difference in pressure (due to depth) or length of plausible leakage pathway.

Computationally, the simulator uses a discretization of every cemented well barrier element, where each cell represents a defect in the cement with a defined gap size. The aforementioned general gap size distribution is here used as a basis for each cell. Thus, a possible realization (repeated sampling for every cell) for an arbitrary well barrier could be as shown in Fig. 1-7. Once a realization is done, an algorithm determines a traversal path from bottom to top of the matrix based on the principle of least resistance, e.g. selecting the neighboring-above cell with the greater gap size.

52,1	49,1	17,7	23,6	44,4	30,9	24,1	38,1	56,4	20,4
21,8	20,2	26,0	52,6	16,8	13,6	19,4	62,3	44,1	27,7
17,2	56,0	10,4	16,3	9,9	24,5	14,7	47,6	30,9	11,2
13,8	31,0	43,9	38,5	21,4	52,5	27,3	23,1	43,3	27,6
16,2	16,0	9,1	31,2	31,5	27,8	19,7	54,9	37,1	33,2
30,2	30,7	31,9	43,3	24,5	64,6	16,1	5,9	48,3	37,7
35,9	36,9	7,6	45,5	56,4	57,3	25,5	24,9	20,6	19,2
17,2	45,6	42,0	13,8	35,5	29,3	23,0	20,0	37,2	30,6
29,9	38,5	23,2	47,7	26,3	42,5	56,6	27,2	26,5	54,9
21,1	31,0	20,7	37,0	22,8	56,6	18,7	27,9	46,8	37,9

Fig. 1-7: Example of how a cemented well barrier can be discretized laterally and radially, where cells represent cement defects, and values are microannuli gap sizes in μm .

Making assumptions on possible microannuli gap sizes are fundamental to being able to make quantitative assessments of leakage potential.

1.6.4 Input parameters

Pressure, temperature and assumed gas entry point

Each well has an assumed point of entry depth, which is where it is assumed that CO₂ or CH₄ could enter the well. This is, for all wells that are in contact with a reservoir formation, set to the average top depth of the reservoir formation. It is here assumed that the cemented barrier is in a failed state at some point in time and has a vertical migration pathway to surface.

The pressure of the reservoir after injection is assumed to be between 200-250 bar @ 1800 m. For simulations of leakage, the maximum (e.g. 250 bar) pressure has been used as a basis for estimating the pressure gradient, which in turn was used to determine maximum pressure at assumed entry depth for each well. A long-term pressure build up curve, starting from initial pressure up to virgin reservoir pressure, was established for each well. The pressure assumed at given entry point, is listed in Tab. 1-4. The assumed time to reach virgin reservoir pressure has for all wells been set to ca. 200 years, but in this study most results use the maximum pressure case (i.e. virgin reservoir pressure) as a basis and the build-up time is not the point of interest here.

A maximum temperature of ca. 52 °C has been assumed for all wells. Temperature is far less influential on results compared to pressure, and here an assumption of U (10, 52) °C has been used to generate a multitude of temperature scenarios.

Tab. 1-4: Wells, assumed entry point of gas and pressures used as input to leakage simulations

Well name	Assumed gas entry point [m]	Initial pressure [bar]	Virgin reservoir pressure [bar]
UH3	1520	149,1	211,1
UH5	N/A	N/A	N/A
UH6	N/A	N/A	N/A
UH9	1880	184,4	261,1
UH10	2410	236,4	334,7
UH11	1510	148,1	209,7
UH12	N/A	N/A	N/A
UH16	2440	239,4	338,9
ZA1	1870	183,4	259,7
ZA3	1565	153,0	200,0
ZA4	1580	155,0	219,4
ZA4A	1700	166,8	236,1
ZA5H	2520	247,2	350,0
ZA6	1930	189,3	268,1
ZA6A	1850	181,5	256,9
ZA7	1860	182,5	258,3
ZA8H	2340	229,6	325,0
ZA8AH	2340	229,6	325,0
ZA9H	N/A	N/A	N/A
ZA9AH	2165	212,4	300,7
ZA12	2000	196,2	277,8
ZA14H	1885	184,9	261,8

Well designs

Input related to trajectory, casing dimensions and depths, and cement plugs have been provided by MND and CGS. For a complete overview, please refer to Appendix A.

Assumed leakage path

Each well could have a multitude of possible migration pathways for gas to escape from the reservoir via the wellbore to the surface. However, we focus only here is a predefined pathway for each well, which has been determined from judgments and on the principle of shortest pathway, i.e. whichever pathway represents the minimum length of cemented barriers, where barriers are here understood as either cement plugs or cemented annular segments. Tab. 1-5 provides an overview of assumed leakage pathway for every well considered.

The leakage pathways shown in Tab. 1-5 are however not based on schematics of planned re-abandonment. As such, these represent scenarios if no measures were taken to improve well integrity. In latter sections, a brief review of the effect of re-abandonment will be discussed.

Tab. 1-5: Assumed leakage path per well

Well name	Assumed gas entry point [m]	Assumed breached well barrier elements <to, from> m	Total barrier length traversed [m]
UH3	1520	Plug <0, 40> Plug <300, 364> Annulus <775, 1520>	849
UH5	N/A	N/A	N/A
UH6	N/A	N/A	N/A
UH9	1880	Plug <2, 40> Annulus <1685, 1880>	233
UH10	2410	Plug <2, 102> Plug <250, 350> Plug <351, 437> Annulus <1730, 2410>	966
UH11	1510	Plug <0, 50> Plug <230, 270> Annulus <365, 1510>	1235
UH12	N/A	N/A	N/A
UH16	2440	Plug <0, 39> Annulus <2100, 2400>	379
ZA1	1870	Plug <15, 61> Annulus <1735, 1870>	181
ZA3	1565	Annulus <0, 1565>	1565
ZA4	1580	Plug <900, 1050> Plug <1256, 1430>	324
ZA4A	1700	Annulus <0, 1700>	1700
ZA5H	2520	Annulus <25, 2520>	2495
ZA6	1930	Plug <886, 1070> Plug <1572, 1930>	542
ZA6A	1850	Annulus <0, 1850>	1850
ZA7	1860	Annulus <1450, 1860>	410
ZA8H	2340	Plug <2242, 2332>	90
ZA8AH	2340	Annulus <2167, 2338>	171
ZA9H	N/A	N/A	N/A
ZA9AH	2165	Annulus <0, 2165>	2165
ZA12	2000	Plug <2, 55> Plug <191, 278> Annulus <245, 1999>	1894
ZA14H	1885	Annulus <1849, 2116>	267

An example of a well schematic, shown in Fig. 1-8 for well UH3, illustrates how a possible leakage pathway for gas migration, where blue, red and green regions are well barrier elements that would need to be defect. This example illustrates that not all cemented barriers need to be breached for a leak to surface to occur.

Fig. 1-8: Well schematic for UH3. Blue, red and green color shows respectively primary, secondary and open hole to surface well barrier elements that are assumed defect for gas to migrate through to reach surface.

1.6.5 CO₂ Leakage rates – original well design

Fig. 1-9 shows simulated CO₂ leakage rate range for each well. Range is shown in terms of 10th percentile, mean and 90th percentile leakage rates. Wells ZA1 and ZA8H expose the largest leakage rates. All leakage rates are $< 1,2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($< 2,1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kg/s}$).

Fig. 1-9: Simulated CO2 leakage rates for each well considered, based on original well design (not re-abandoned)

If assuming that any well is equally likely to be the cause of a leak (probably not the case in reality) and we randomly sample a source well a large number of times, then sampling from the selected well's leakage distribution, an aggregated CO2 leakage distribution can be established, see Fig. 1-10.

Fig. 1-10: Aggregated CO2 leakage distribution when assuming any well is equally likely to leak and no re-abandonment has been performed.

This aggregated distribution has a mean value of $3,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and a standard deviation of $3,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

1.6.6 CH₄ Leakage rates – original well design

Fig. 1-11 shows simulated CH₄ (methane) leakage rate range for each well. Range is shown in terms of 10th percentile, mean and 90th percentile leakage rates. Wells ZA1 and ZA8H expose the largest leakage rates. All leakage rates are $< 2,5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (1,7 kg/s).

Fig. 1-11: Simulated CH₄ leakage rates for each well considered, based on original well design (not re-abandoned).

An aggregate CH₄ leakage distribution, equivalent to that in Fig. 1-10 for CO₂, is shown in Fig. 1-12.

Fig. 1-12: Aggregated CH₄ leakage distribution when assuming any well is equally likely to leak and no re-abandonment has been performed.

This aggregated distribution has a mean value of $5,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and a standard deviation of $6,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

1.6.7 Parameters of importance

This section presents some discussions on the parameters that most strongly impact the CO₂ leakage potential. The section is limited to parameters that are included in the simulation framework, while acknowledging the certainly additional factors not mentioned here could be relevant and important, such as the quality of the plug and abandonment operation, which directly impacts the existing and future well integrity, possibility of cement being exposed directly to CO₂, etc.

One way of measuring the importance of a parameter on a generated result can be expressed using Spearman Rank correlation, used to evaluate linear relationships between data when a change in one variable is associated with a proportional change in the other variable.

Tab. 1-6: Spearman rank correlation coefficient for selected input parameters

Parameter	Spearman rank correlation coefficient
Virgin reservoir pressure	0,34
Total leakage path length	-0,78
ZA1: Microannuli gap size: Plug <15, 61>	0,50
ZA1: Microannuli gap size: Annulus <1735, 1870>	0,67

Tab. 1-6, listing various input parameters versus simulated leakage rate, shows that the total leakage path length is unsurprisingly the most important parameter; the smaller the length, the greater the leakage rate will presumably be. Virgin reservoir pressure shows a relatively much weaker relationship, but higher pressures will naturally increase flow potential. Microannuli gap size is obviously also an important parameter, although the actual impact on leakage rate was not directly obtainable in simulations. Thus, ZA1 gap sizes were collected and compare with simulated leakage rate across the corresponding barrier element (plug or annulus) as an indication.

1.6.8 Re-abandonment: updated leakage simulations

As previously mentioned, the simulations in chapters 1.6.5-1.6.6 are based on the original well and barrier design schematics, and do not include plans for re-abandoning wells which would be performed prior to CO₂ injection. As the actual well barrier design is not exactly known at the current moment, this chapter presumes the re-abandonment essentially will increase the length of inner cement plugs such that assumed leak path length would be reduced. Such an approach is illustrated in Fig. 1-13 for UH3, where the secondary (red) barrier (lower plug) has been extended upward compared to the original design shown in Fig. 1-8.

Fig. 1-13: Illustration of re-abandonment design for well UH3, where the length of inner cement plug (red) has been extended.

Furthermore, it is presumed that no active measures will be taken to extend or improve cemented annulus sections, i.e. these will remain unchanged. Thus, when evaluating the impact of re-abandonment on simulated leakage rates, these may be reduced (especially if the assumed leakage path largely consists of inner cement plugs) or remain unchanged (if assumed leakage path consists only of annular cement sections).

CO₂ Leakage rates – re-abandonment design

Fig. 1-14 shows updated CO₂ leakage rates when accounting for re-abandoned wells as described above.

Fig. 1-14: Simulated CO₂ leakage rates for each well considered, based on assumed re-abandoned well designs.

Compared with Fig. 1-9 (original design), the reduction in simulated CO₂ leakage rate is notable for wells UH16, ZA1, ZA4, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA8AH and ZA14H. However, for wells UH10, UH11 and ZA12 no marked difference is observed. Common for these wells is that the increase in barrier length is less than for the other wells. Wells UH9, ZA3, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6A, ZA7 and ZA9AH do not have increased barrier length under the currently assumed re-abandonment simulation, i.e. an increase barrier length for these wells would have to be based on increasing the length of annular cement. Fig. 1-14 also indicates that UH9, UH10 and ZA7 expose relatively higher leakage rates than other wells.

Fig. 1-15 shows effect of increasing the barrier length on simulated CO₂ leakage rates for wells impacted. The plot displays on x-axis the ratio between the barrier length after re-abandonment to original barrier length, while the y-axis shows the order of magnitude reduction in simulated CO₂ leakage rate.

Fig. 1-15: Effect of increase in barrier length on simulated CO2 leakage rate for selected wells.

An updated aggregated distribution, when assuming any well is equally likely to leak, is shown for CO2 based on re-abandonment assumptions in Fig. 1-16.

Fig. 1-16: Aggregated CO2 leakage distribution when assuming any well is equally likely to leak and re-abandonment *has* been performed

This aggregated distribution has a mean value of $1,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($1,8 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg/s}$) and a standard deviation of $1,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. Compared to the aggregated distribution when considering the

original well designs (Fig. 1-10) the change in mean CO₂ leakage rate represents a 2/3 reduction.

CH₄ Leakage rates – re-abandonment design

Fig. 1-17 shows updated CH₄ leakage rates when accounting for re-abandoned wells as described above.

Fig. 1-17: Simulated CH₄ leakage rates for each well considered, based on assumed re-abandoned well designs.

Compared with Fig. 1-11 (original design), the reduction in simulated CH₄ leakage rate is notable for wells UH3, UH16, ZA1, ZA4, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA8AH and ZA14H. However, for wells UH10, UH11 and ZA12 no marked difference is observed. Common for these wells is that the increase in barrier length is less than for the other wells. Wells UH9, ZA3, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6A, ZA7 and ZA9AH do not have increased barrier length under the currently assumed re-abandonment simulation, i.e. an increase barrier length for these wells would have to be based on increasing the length of annular cement. Fig. 1-17 also indicates that UH9, UH10 and ZA7 expose relatively higher leakage rates than other wells.

Fig. 1-18 shows effect of increasing the barrier length on simulated CO₂ leakage rates for wells impacted. The plot displays on x-axis the ratio between the barrier length after re-abandonment to original barrier length, while the y-axis shows the order of magnitude reduction in simulated CH₄ leakage rate.

Fig. 1-18: Effect of increase in barrier length on simulated CH4 leakage rate for selected wells.

An updated aggregated distribution, when assuming any well is equally likely to leak, is shown for CH4 based on re-abandonment assumptions in Fig. 1-19.

Fig. 1-19: Aggregated CH4 leakage distribution when assuming any well is equally likely to leak and re-abandonment *has* been performed.

This aggregated distribution has a mean value of $2,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and a standard deviation of $5,0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. Compared to the aggregated distribution when considering the original well designs (Fig. 1-12) the change in mean CH₄ leakage rate represents a 3/5 reduction.

1.6.9 Well integrity logging of ZA7

Well ZA7 was well integrity logged in November 2023 to provide updates of the status of this wells cement barriers. The conclusion from this report is that 20 years after the well was drilled, the condition of cemented well barriers is still good. For further details it is referred to (Hrdlicková, Štastný, & Kolečka, 2023).

1.6.10 Risk monitoring of Zar-3 boreholes

To evaluate the potential leakage pathways via existing wells, the soil gas monitoring of both the well hubs (production platforms) of the Zar-3 oil & gas field was carried out. The soil gas composition was measured during the winter season (February 14th and 16th, 2023), when, in general, negligible interference by biological methanogenic activity was observed.

20 monitoring points were measured: 10 at the northern well hub and 10 at the southern well hub (Tab. 1-7). A portable Ecoprobe-5 instrument (RS Dynamics) with an infrared detector with measuring range from 0 to 45% vol and accuracy of 15 % rel of readings was used. The soil gas was measured from the depth range of 10-80 cm from the holes drilled by a hand-drill prior to the measurement. For more data concerning the soil-gas monitoring, see R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results of this project (Jirman et al., 2023).

Tab. 1-7: Soil gas monitoring points of the southern and northern well hubs. SH = Southern Hub, NH = Northern Hub, both corresponding to production licenses

Point (name)	Coordinates (Gauss-Kruger)		Point (name)	Coordinates (Gauss-Kruger)	
	X	Y		X	Y
SH1	3644161.85	5437243.13	NH1	3644008.18	5437783.84
SH2	3644166.17	5437226.10	NH2	3644000.33	5437804.44
SH3	3644171.43	5437203.54	NH3	3643989.60	5437831.76
SH4	3644189.45	5437208.23	NH4	3644000.23	5437853.51
SH5	3644202.26	5437208.01	NH5	3644037.66	5437862.50
SH6	3644213.29	5437211.41	NH6	3644072.04	5437870.84
SH7	3644216.64	5437228.75	NH7	3644079.25	5437849.44
SH8	3644224.64	5437233.18	NH8	3644085.58	5437811.00
SH9	3644211.79	5437252.21	NH9	3644064.95	5437803.12
SH10	3644211.32	5437272.79	NH10	3644042.50	5437786.06

The monitored area of well hubs includes the following boreholes in operation: ZA3, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6A, ZA7, ZA8AH, ZA9AH, ZA14H as well as the abandoned sections of several wells (ZA4, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA9H). Both well hubs (production platforms) are located within the production licences of the Zar-3 oil & gas field, as shown in Fig. 1-20. Remaining boreholes (UH3, UH5, UH6, UH9, UH10, UH11, UH12, UH16, ZA1 and ZA12) were abandoned and, except for UH3 and ZA12, are located outside both the Zar-3 oil & gas field and the protected field area.

Fig. 1-20: Wells included within the area of interest (red rectangle), monitored well hubs are located within the production licences (green polygons), Zar-3 oil & gas field (yellow polygon) and protected field area (cyan polygon).

Southern well hub

The monitoring at the southern well hub took place on February 16th, 2023. 10 monitoring points were selected (SH1 – SH10), their locations shown in Fig. 1-21.

Fig. 1-21: Position of 10 monitoring points in the southern well hub. Small methane show of 0.6 %_{vol}. was measured in soil gas at the SH7 monitoring point. Production licence = green polygon, Zar-3 oil & gas field boundary = yellow polygon.

A small methane show with 0.6 %_{vol} CH₄ in soil gas was measured at single monitoring point, SH7. This value represents less than 12 % of methane lower explosive limit (LEL) and does not present a risk element since it was measured at a single monitoring point and no other methane shows were detected in the rest of the area. The measurement results for the monitoring points of the southern well hub is shown in Tab. 1-8.

Tab. 1-8: Results of soil gas monitoring at the southern well hub. TP = total petroleum gases

Point (name)	Samp pres. (hPa)	O ₂ (% _{vol})	Temp. (°C)	CH ₄ av. (% _{vol})	TP av. (% _{vol})	CO ₂ av. (% _{vol})	Date
SH1	-332.6	18.15	11.10	0.00	0.00	0.12	16.2. 12:12
SH2	-15.9	20.55	11.12	0.00	0.00	0.72	16.2. 12:14
SH3	-29.0	20.28	11.25	0.00	0.00	0.51	16.2. 12:15
SH4	-31.3	19.51	11.37	0.00	0.00	0.14	16.2. 12:18
SH5	-52.7	20.37	11.68	0.00	0.00	0.08	16.2. 12:21
SH6	-233.9	18.14	11.82	0.00	0.00	0.08	16.2. 12:24

SH7	-206.6	19.49	11.87	0.60	0.28	0.09	16.2. 12:26
SH8	-108.4	18.74	12.17	0.00	0.00	0.04	16.2. 12:31
SH9	-304.0	15.95	12.33	0.00	0.00	0.40	16.2. 12:35
SH10	-33.1	19.87	12.17	0.00	0.00	0.44	16.2. 12:39

Northern well hub

The monitoring at the northern well hub took place on February 14th, 2023. 10 monitoring points were selected (NH1 – NH10), their locations shown in Fig. 1-22.

Fig. 1-22: Position of 10 monitoring points in the northern well hub. Production license = green polygon, Zar-3 oil & gas field protected area = cyan polygon.

Neither methane nor the TP (total petroleum gases, methane to butane) shows were detected in the area. The measurement results for the monitoring points of the northern well hub is shown Tab. 1-9.

Tab. 1-9: Results of soil gas monitoring at the northern well hub. TP = total petroleum gases

Point (name)	Samp pres. (hPa)	O ₂ (%vol)	Temp. (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%vol)	TP av. (%vol)	CO ₂ av. (%vol)	Date
NH1	-4.1	21.05	10.09	0.00	0.00	0.09	14.2. 16:00
NH2	-1.5	21.09	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.10	14.2. 16:02
NH3	-6.1	20.84	10.27	0.00	0.00	0.32	14.2. 16:05
NH4	-5.6	20.77	10.4	0.00	0.00	0.29	14.2. 16:06
NH5	-2.1	20.91	10.57	0.00	0.00	0.11	14.2. 16:08
NH6	-2.5	20.49	10.73	0.00	0.00	0.84	14.2. 16:10
NH7	-1.6	20.67	10.91	0.00	0.00	0.35	14.2. 16:12
NH8	-3.3	20.67	11.01	0.00	0.00	0.28	14.2. 16:14
NH9	-8.0	20.66	11.11	0.00	0.00	0.14	14.2. 16:16
NH10	-62.7	18.08	11.28	0.00	0.00	1.06	14.2. 16:18

Conclusion based on monitoring

The boreholes in operation above the Zar-3 oil & gas field are regarded as currently sealing with no leakage indications based on the first soil gas monitoring campaign.

1.7 Leakage through caprock

1.7.1 Sealing formations

Directly above the Vranovice Formation mainly pelitic sediments of the Jurassic Mikulov Formation and the Paleogene are deposited, forming a primary seal for the reservoir (Fig. 1-23). The Mikulov Formation overlies the northern and eastern portions of the Zar-3 field, while the Paleogene sediments lie directly above the reservoir in the southern and western parts of the structure. Only in the northern and eastern parts of the Zar-3 structure the Mikulov Formation is partly overlain by the Palaeogene deposits, in other parts both of these formations forming the caprock are overlain by Carpathian flysch nappes.

Fig. 1-23: 3D view of the caprock (Mikulov marls and Paleogene) overlying the reservoir (Vranovice carbonates) at the Zar-3 field.

Jurassic Mikulov formation

Silty sediments of the Mikulov formation overlie the northern and eastern part of the Zar-3 field, from where they continue in a northern and north-eastern direction. In addition to the Vranovice Formation, within the area of interest the Mikulov Formation also overlies the Jurassic Nikolcice Formation, Carboniferous and Devonian rocks.

The Mikulov Formation is spread in the northern part of the study area. The southern erosional boundary is formed by deep incision of overlying Palaeogene sediments and runs east of the Zar-3 southern boundary, where it has an east-west direction. In the area of the Zar-3 structure, the pinch-out boundary changes its direction to north-south and continues in this way up to the boundary of the study area. The northern pinch-out has a roughly east-west trend and runs south of the wells UH6 and UH12 in the northern part of the available 3D seismic cube.

The depth (TVDSS) of the base of the Mikulov Formation in the area of interest ranges from 1900 m to 850 m and reaches its maximum in a local depression located to the east of the Zar-3 field. From there, the base of the formation gradually rises to the north, west and east up to areas of formation pinch-out in the north and west. In the area of the Zar-3 field itself, the base of the Mikulov Formation lies at depths (TVDSS) ranging from 1300 to the initial oil-water contact at depths of around 1600 m.

The Mikulov Formation thickness map is shown in Fig. 1-24. The formation reaches a maximum thickness of about 550 m in the depression northeast of the Zar-3 structure, from where there is a reduction in the formation thickness in all directions up to complete pinch-out. The abrupt reduction in thickness occurs in the area of the Zar-3 field and to the east / southeast of it due to significant Paleogene erosional event. The reduction of thickness in other directions is more or less fluent. In the area of the Zar-3 field, there is a reduction in the thickness of the sealing Mikulov marls from 350 – 400 m in the northern parts of the structure to the south and southwest. Roughly from the middle parts of the field main elevation towards the south, the Mikulov marls are completely eroded below the Paleogene deposits. The thickness change in the western part of the field is mainly due to facies changes and the resulting increase in thickness of the Vranovice carbonates at the expense of the Mikulov marls.

Fig. 1-24: Thickness map of the Jurassic Mikulov Formation with marked contacts at the Zar-3 field.

Maximum depths (TVDSS) of the Mikulov Formation top surface are around 1800 m near its southern boundary, where the formation thickness is reduced by erosion. From there it gradually rises, generally northwards up to 900 – 850 m in the area of northern pinch-out. The southern and western part of the Mikulov marls body is overlain by Palaeogene sediments, while in the direct overburden of its northern part there are flysch rocks. The top surface of the

Mikulov marls in the area of the Zar-3 structure lies at depths ranging from about 1600 m to 1150 m and is considerably eroded.

Paleogene

Paleogene sediments in the area of interest are predominantly pelitic and are developed mainly in the southern part of the available 3D seismic cube. Except for the north-eastern edge of the Zar-3 field, they are spread over its entire area where in the south and west they directly overlay the reservoir and in the northern parts they lie above the Mikulov marls. To the south and west of the Zar-3 structure is a large area, formed by incision, where Palaeogene sediments overlie Carboniferous rocks.

The Paleogene deposits are spread in the southern part of the area of interest, to the north and east of the field are pinching-out and are not present in the north of the area. The pinch-out boundary has a wavy course of WSW – ENE direction in the area to the east of the field. It extends to the NE edge of the field, from where it continues approximately in a SE – NW direction up to the boundary of the study area.

The base of the Palaeogene lies at the greatest depths in the southern edge of the area, where it reaches 2350 m and from there it rises to the north and NW. It is possible to distinguish 2 distinct areas of Paleogene deposition in the study area. South and SW of the Zar-3 structure, Palaeogene rocks are deposited in an incised valley and here they reach considerable depths, while the area to the north and east of the field, as well as most of the field itself, represents marginal parts of Palaeogene sedimentation at relatively shallower depth levels. In the area of the Zar-3 field, the depths of Paleogene base range from about 1150 m to 1600 m.

The thickness map for the Paleogene is shown in Fig. 1-25. In the incised valley to the south of the Zar-3 structure Paleogene sediments attain the maximum thickness of over 500 m. From there the trend of a gradual reduction in thickness continues to the north and northwest of the study area. Northeastwards, there is an abrupt change in thickness on the slope of the incised valley to the east of the Zar-3 field and in its southern part and on the opposite side of this slope the Paleogene deposits reach only up to 200 m thickness in the northern marginal parts. The valley margin was probably predisposed tectonically, but any original fault plane was subsequently almost completely removed by Paleogene erosion. The entire Zar-3 structure lies in the area of reduced thickness of Paleogene sediment with a range of 0 - 300 m. Its southern edge is formed by the mentioned Paleogene erosional event. A line of pinch-out crosses the north-eastern margin of the field, Paleogene sediments are absent in this marginal part.

Fig. 1-25: Depth structure map of the top of the Paleogene with marked contacts at the Zar-3 field.

Maximum depths (TVDSS) of the Paleogene top surface are around 1900 m at the southern edge of the area of interest. From here, the formation surface continues in a trend of smooth uplift to the northwest and north to the pinch-out boundary in the northern part of the available seismic cube. Throughout the whole area of interest, Paleogene sediments are overlain by flysch rocks.

Combined caprock thickness

Based on seismic interpretation and well results, a combined map of primary caprock, formed by the Mikulov Formation and the Paleogene, was also constructed (Fig. 1-26). The map shows two local areas where the thickness of the sealing rocks exceeds 500 m. One of them is located to the south of the Zar-3 structure and is filled with Paleogene sediments, while the other, filled with the Mikulov marls, lies to the northeast of the field. The northern pinch-out of the Mikulov marls in front of wells UH6 and UH12 is also the pinch-out of the primary caprock. However, the reservoir (Vranovice carbonates) does not extend beyond this boundary, its pinch-out occurs even more to the south. The field is located between the mentioned areas of maximum thickness. Above the reservoir in the area of the ZAR-3 structure the caprock is in a reduced thickness ranging from approximately 100 to a maximum of 400 m. The thickness reduction is partly due to erosion, in the upper parts of the field also by lateral shift from reservoir facies to caprock facies.

Fig. 1-26: Combined thickness map of the Paleogene + Mikulov Formation with marked contacts at the Zar-3 field

1.7.2 Geochemistry, mud logs and mineralogy

The main findings concerning geochemical properties of the sealing caprocks is presented here. More details and figures are provided in Appendix B.

Geochemical properties of the caprocks are among the key elements in the assessment of the risk of possible CO₂ leakage from the planned storage (depleted oil and gas reservoir). Mud logs, i.e. data obtained during the drilling of exploration and production wells, provide an important basis for the analysis of potential leakage paths through the caprocks.

The mud logs indicate the strongest signal of petroleum hydrocarbon shows in several intervals within the reservoir. Second strongest shows are registered in the immediate vicinity of the reservoir, especially in the Paleogene rocks of the Nesvacilka Fm (Fig. 1-27), weaker shows are found in the underlying Lower Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. Similar features were observed numerous oil and gas fields in the southern Moravia (Czech Republic). Luminescence signals are almost absent in the Upper Jurassic Mikulov Fm., which seems to be a more efficient seal. Almost no luminescence signal is registered in the overthrust Zdanice unit (Carpathian Flysch Belt). It is interpreted as the most important seal (no. 3) in the storage complex.

Fig. 1-27: Interpreted N-S cross section of ZAR-3 oil and gas field with luminescence logs in .las format in the ZA6, ZA6A, ZA3, ZA4A, ZA4 wells.

Current geochemical investigations complement the mud log data with molecular characteristics. The preliminary results show that a number of Paleogene caprock samples contain hydrocarbons of the same origin as the principal Zar-3 oil accumulation. Yet, a few samples were found with low permeability in the Paleogene caprock interval, which contain the original syngenetic bitumen of very low thermal maturity, very different from the thermally mature oil in the reservoir.

1.7.3 Geomechanical stability - Evaluation

This section presents an abridged version of contents from Report R.4.3 (Nermoen & Porzer, 2022). The contents here are based directly or indirectly on M4.1 and Report R.4.3. Report 4.3 presents an evaluation of whether re-pressurization and cooling leads to rock failure, and where geomechanical stability is evaluated by combining mechanical test results and earth stress estimates.

The impact of cooling and re-pressurization are the primary focus for mechanical stability analysis. Cooling and re-pressurization dictate the effective stresses during CO₂ injection. Of secondary relevance are the chemical impact of the reactive brine, that may, dependent on the rock-fluid interactions, affect the strength envelope of the rock. Insights into this will be provided from WP5 and sound velocity changes in WP4, as any chemical reaction may both strengthen or weaken the rock, upon which (and how) minerals dissolve or precipitate.

Data shows that the overburden rocks are much stronger than the reservoir (both tensile strength, frictional coefficient and cohesion).

The ‘effective’ stresses in the overburden, with nearly zero porosity and sub-nanoscale permeability, will not be affected by any pore pressure variation in the reservoir. The effective stress concept is nearly irrelevant in overburden rocks. And if so, only a small potential fractional impact of the fluid pressure pulse will the overburden pore pressures. In shales, with sub-nanometer scale pore space, pore pressure in potential fluid inclusions are not affected by the pressure variation in the nearby reservoir.

Further, due to the heat capacity in the reservoir rock, fluid and the injected CO₂, the injected CO₂ amounts are inadequate to reduce the temperature in the overburden. Especially, if the injection of CO₂ will focus on the water zone, that is being considered here. Further on, rock-fluid interactions in the overburden are limited by the transport of any potentially chemically reactive elements, simply due to its negligible permeability.

There is, however, one way in which the overburden may be detrimentally affected. That is due to any reservoir swelling/bulging/decompaction that may occur when the pristine pore pressure is regained after depletion. If the reservoir grows in size (ballooning/swelling) the side stress of the overburden rock will reduce, and if they become negative, then vertically oriented hydraulic fractures will grow if the extensive stress exceeds the tensile strength. We have evaluated tensile strength of a series of overburden rocks in Brazilian tests (see UH3_b4_c6 of Mikulov Marl with $T_0=9.14$ MPa, almost four times higher than the reservoir). To evaluate whether this is a realistic effect that could occur, we may use the knowledge gained by the experience from the gas-production until now. There are however, to best of our knowledge, no reservoir subsidence nor overburden compaction effects observed during production. Thus, any opposite de-compaction effect caused by re-pressurization, is hard to imagine. Cooling would reduce the volume of the reservoir that could compensate for any potential swelling induced by re-pressurization. Thus, the horizontal compressive stresses of the overburden rock volumes would increase, and the likelihood of vertical fracture propagation is reduced. These details are complex to consider and is out of scope to estimate from the geomechanical rock sample experiments. A full 4D geomechanical numerical modeling would be needed to determine the impact of this (seemingly very unlikely) scenario.

We would, despite that, recommend installing ground observations during the re-injection phase so that this effect can be monitored and potentially be used to generate any early warning signal that can be used during operation (vary injection pressure, volume, induce waiting time to allow for equilibration of the reservoir, etc.).

1.7.4 Geomechanical failures: Monte Carlo simulation

Rock strengths were determined from tensile, triaxial and unconfined strength tests. During CO₂ injection into warm reservoir rock the operator can control pore pressure and temperature. Cooling reduces the side stress via thermo-elastic effects (assuming uni-axial strains with constant reservoir widths and overburden weight), while increased pore pressure reduces mean effective stress. Thus, p' is reduced while q increases, bringing the stress-state towards failure. Further, ultrasonic stiffness measurements before and after CO₂ exposure and the correlation between stiffness and strength, indicate that geochemical effects reduce rock strengths.

The initial stresses, s_1 , and s_3 , and pressure (P_f), and thermo-elastic coupling coefficient are uncertain and assigned with probability density functions (PDF's). When sampling from the PDFs using Monte Carlo analyses, the possible qp -space is defined, in terms of mean effective stress (x -axis) and earth stresses (y -axis), see Fig. 1-28, and the number of unstable cases can be calculated.

Fig. 1-28: Possible changes in stress state, from an initial state (green), showing effect of cooling only (blue), re-pressurization only (grey) and cooling and re-pressurization (yellow). Bounding lines represent condition where shear failure (dashed) and tensile (solid) failure may occur (Nermoen, et al., 2023). The number of unstable cases, as function of reservoir temperature and pore pressure is shown to the right.

Parameters expressed stochastically in the stability analysis reflect uncertainty as judged by the analyst. The controlling parameters p' and q are uncertain, due in part related to earth stresses, stiffness parameters, as well as inherent variability in results obtained from laboratory analyses. The evaluations of these, as well as the limits of the failure envelope, directly impact how the overall geomechanical stability of the storage site is judged, which in turn directly impacts the feasibility of the site for storing CO₂. Thus, these parameters influence the decision of what should be the prevailing pore pressure and temperature during CO₂ injection, such that we optimize injection potential of the site while keeping well within safe operating conditions where geomechanical failure does not occur.

Fig. 1-29: Phase diagram for probability of geomechanical failure for a) intact rocks – tensile and shear failure, and b) intact rocks with fractured stress state where the intact rock fraction (90%) carry the total vertical load.

Fig. 1-29 a) and b) are a result of running Monte Carlo simulations and counting the number of instances where the stress level exceeded the failure envelope (tensile and shear failure, and

re-opening of existing fracture). In conditions as in a), repressurization up to 21-22 MPa is safe, whereas in the case of b) repressurization up to 19-20 MPa is safe, i.e. a reduction of 2 MPa.

1.7.5 Caprock leakage simulations

The thickness map shown in Fig. 1-26 was used as a basis for determining the required vertical distance CO₂ would have to migrate through to reach surface (ignoring any non-sealing formations entirely here). The map was used as input to a length matrix, and caprock thickness was randomly sampled from this matrix. Using Darcy's law for flow through a porous medium, and sampling randomly from the thickness map, and estimated potential leakage rate through the Mikulov formation could be estimated. Results indicate leakage rates $1,0 \cdot 10^{-13}$ – $1,0 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m³/s, see Fig. 1-30.

Fig. 1-30: Simulated CO₂ leakage rate through combined caprock (Mikulov + Paleogene).

The distribution shown in Fig. 1-30 has a mean value of $3,5 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m³/s, with a standard deviation of $1,6 \cdot 10^{-11}$ m³/s.

The crucial assumptions here is the permeability of the sealing formations. As a basis for establishing this quantity, core sample measurements were used from seals from Mikulov Fm. and Zarusice Mb. (core names UH3_c4_b6a, ZA3_c1_b1b and ZA3_c1_b1c). Using the permeabilities from these (listed in the CO₂-SPICER master table) yields the following generic probability distribution for caprock permeability, shown in Fig. 1-31.

Fig. 1-31: Generic probability distribution for caprock permeability, based on core samples of seals in CO₂-SPICER master table.

1.8 Leakage from faults

1.8.1 Faults in the broader area of interest Zar-3

Faults and tectonic framework of the broader area of interest is characterized in the following set of thematic maps and cross sections based on gravity and magnetic data (Fig. 1-32 to Fig. 1-38). The Zar-3 field is located next to the Nesvacilka Canyon, which is an incised valley into the Jurassic and Paleozoic Formations filled with Eocene silts, sands and shales (Picha et al., 2006 and references therein). The erosional truncation of the older rocks at the base of Eocene is demonstrated in the AA' and BB' profiles parallel to the Carpathian thrust front. The following set of images shows indications of tectonics and possible steep slopes or sudden facies changes found on gravimetric and magnetic maps in the wider vicinity of the area of interest. Density contact derived from gravimetric maps are of primary interest.

Fig. 1-32: Area of interest - schematic geological map and position of cross sections AA' and BB' with Bouguer anomalies.

Fig. 1-33: Cross section A – A’ with measured and calculated Bouguer anomalies.

Fig. 1-34: Cross section B – B’ with measured and calculated Bouguer anomalies.

Fig. 1-35: Density contrasts (red question marks) in the broader Zar-3 area.

Fig. 1-36: Bouguer anomaly map (1) and reflectance display of gravity anomalies (2).

Fig. 1-37: Residual gravity anomalies, density contacts and reflectance imaging of horizontal gradients of gravity.

The blocks with different density are separated by dark shadow lines interpreted in most cases as faults (Fig. 1-36 and Fig. 1-37). There is a regional W-E fault cutting the Zar-3 rectangle but not the Zar-3 field itself. The fault is south and downslope of the Zar-3 field, it is therefore interpreted as non-endangering the field consistency.

Fig. 1-38: Magnetic intensity map (A) and isopach map of Autochthonous Paleogene sediments – Nesvacilka Fm. (B).

Individual phenomena will be confronted with seismic measurements, well results and older structural maps of the wider surroundings of the ZAR-3 reservoir. Among other things, the issue of possible fault reactivation will also be assessed on this basis.

1.8.2 Evaluation of leakage potential

Regarding the faulting of the Zar-3 area, tectonic termination of the Carboniferous sediments on a prominent NW – SE trending fault has been identified. This fault is quite well imaged by the seismic and is also demonstrated by the drilling results. The fault is not evident in younger than Carboniferous sediments and does not affect the field itself and eventual CO₂ storage.

Apart from the mentioned fault the seismic image does not show significant signs of tectonics; overall the area appears to be more or less atectonic with a predominance of erosional processes that may have hidden or completely removed eventual older fault planes. Some indications of reflectors discontinuities in some parts of the seismic cube are short in extent, of varying irregular direction with no apparent trend, and often not very clear, indicating facies / lithology changes rather than faulting. In summary, the 3D seismic in this version of the processing does not seem to highlight, but rather suppresses, the display of possible fault tectonics.

Except one case, all interpretations of the study area agree that the geological setting of the Zar-3 field and its close vicinity is atectonic and its western and northern boundary is erosive. The position of this erosional boundary varies slightly from one interpretation to another, which is due to the poor resolution of the seismic and the lack of wells for detailed correlations. Examples of different interpretations of the Zar-3 structure are shown in the Fig. 1-39-Fig. 1-42. Only one interpretation (Fig. 1-40) resolves the field northern boundary by fault.

Fig. 1-39: Top of the Vranovice carbonates – depth contour map published by Kostelnicek et al. (2006).

Fig. 1-40: Top of the Vranovice carbonates – depth contour map by Rez 2018 (MND).

Fig. 1-41: Top of the Vranovice carbonates – depth contour map by MND (2022).

1.9 Leakage from spill points

The initial gas-oil and oil-water contact of the Zar-3 field was at the 1490 m and 1595 m level, respectively. According to the structure map of the reservoir top (Fig. 1-43) a spill-point even slightly lower than the original oil-water contact can be considered, to a maximum depth of 1650 m (TVDSS). When the structure is filled below this level, there would likely be media flow in the north closure of the structure into the adjacent carbonate body.

Fig. 1-43: Depth structure map of the top of the Jurassic Vranovice formation with marked contacts and the spill-point at the Zar-3 field

The Vranovice formation is formed by more or less isolated bodies of dolomites and limestones. Based on the available seismic and well data, it is not possible to say for certain whether the carbonate body of Zar-3 field is connected to other bodies to the northwest and east or is isolated from one of them. In the structure map (Fig. 1-43) they are displayed connected, but isolating one of them is not completely excluded.

In the case of leakage of stored CO₂ through a spill-point, the most likely migration paths are either northwest to the well UH11 area or east to northeast to the well area UH5, or in both directions, depending on the isolation degree of the reservoir body from its surroundings.

Fig. 1-44: Geological cross-section through the Zar-3 structure with marked contacts and the spill point, for various directions.

1.10 Blowout from an injection/monitoring well

This chapter focuses on the consequences of blowouts from injection or monitoring wells. Blowouts could theoretically also occur from abandoned wells, but the flow is likely to be more restricted in this case, due to the presence of wellbore seals. Additionally, based on historical data, blowout frequencies for non-operational wells (e.g. abandoned or suspended wells) is almost an order of magnitude less than for active wells (Jordan & Benson, 2009).

A blowout from an injection well could occur during the construction of the well, in which case only oil and natural gas (CH₄) could be released, or during the operation of the injection well, where also CO₂ could escape. The magnitude of any release will also strongly depend on the placement of injection wells. If an influx was taken from the gas saturated zone, then rates are likely to be several magnitudes greater than if an influx was taken from the oil saturated zone, where the gas would be released as part of a two-phase flow.

The blowout simulations performed in this chapter, are based on two-phase release of hydrocarbons for a strictly vertical well, using ZA7 as a basis as this well could potentially serve as a monitoring or injection well. CO₂ blowout has not been simulated. CO₂ discharge when assuming a two-phase mixture with oil, would however likely be in the same order of magnitude as hydrocarbon gas. The well integrity of injection wells depends on the barriers functioning as intended. In a situation where the integrity of both primary and secondary barriers is lost, a blowout, i.e. an uncontrolled release of fluids/gases may occur. In such an event, discharge will proceed through one of the earlier mentioned leakage paths. A blowout

could occur through the wellbore either inside a drill string or in the annulus, or with no restriction in the wellbore (open hole). The simulations performed in this chapter however are presumed probabilistically weighted 10%/80%/10% for string/annulus/open hole blowout, respectively.

1.10.1 Methodology and input parameters

The simulations of leakage rates for oil and gas have been performed using the BlowFlow simulation tool (Karlsen & Ford, 2014), which utilizes Black Oil PVT correlations and Multiphase Flow Correlations combined with a Monte Carlo framework. The inflow (productivity) model for oil is based on an adaption of (Goode & Kuchuk, 1991), while the rates for natural gas are based on the oil rates and the GOR. Specific models for flowing CO₂ were not embedded into the simulation tool, but are estimated based on the basic properties of CO₂ and accompanying PVT properties. A brief overview of the input parameters used in the simulations is given in the following.

Reservoir temperature is assumed to have a linear temperature gradient, down to ca. 1860 meters (rough approximate average depth of wells) at 52 °C, with a heat transfer coefficient set to ca. 35 W/m²/K. Reservoir pressure is set to represent the range of wells on Zar-3, in this case U(180, 260) bar. This pressure distribution is probably higher than what can be expected, but will serve as a conservative assumption in this respect. Net thickness of the oil column is modelled as U(1, 4) meters, while oil and gas gravity are set to 910,0 kg/m³ and 0.554 s.g., respectively. Permeability is given a broad range, U(100, 1000) mD, Dietz factor is estimated to 11.5 and GOR to 150 Sm³/m³. A 6 5/8 inch casing with an inner diameter of 4 3/4 inches is used as a general well architecture representation, and a drill string of 3 inch diameter. Since there are different escape paths in the event of a blowout, these have been taken into account. The simulations consist of both blowout through the drill string, blowout through the drill string annulus or blowout through an open hole (i.e. no restrictions)

The Vasquez-Beggs correlation (Vasquez & Beggs, 1980) was used to estimate PVT properties, while the Hagedorn-Brown correlation (Hagedorn & Brown, 1965) was used to model two-phase flow.

1.10.2 Oil blowout rates

A blowout containing oil is only relevant in a scenario where an influx is taken from the oil saturated zone, either during drilling or during operation of the injection well. Potential oil blowout rates for a generic injection or monitoring well on Zar-3 is shown in Fig. 1-45.

Fig. 1-45: Potential oil blowout rates for generic injection or monitoring well on Zar-3.

Expected oil blowout rates are estimated at 149 m³/d, with an estimated maximum rate of 618 m³/d.

1.10.3 Natural gas (CH₄) blowout rates

Blowout rates for natural gas are only relevant in a scenario where influx occurs during drilling or operation of an active well. The release of natural gas is because of gas dissolution as oil is brought to surface conditions. In the case of a two-phase oil/gas blowout, gas rates would have an expected (mean) value of ~22 500 Sm³/d and a maximum value of 92 000 Sm³/d, as shown in Fig. 1-46.

Fig. 1-46: Potential hydrocarbon gas (CH₄) blowout rates for generic injection or monitoring well on Zar-3.

1.10.4 Blowout duration

The duration of a given blowout is highly dependent on the emergency preparedness system and procedures in place at the site, and naturally also the severity of the blowout itself. Statistically, based on estimates from offshore wells, the time from a blowout occurs to it is controlled, is in the range of 0.5 to 5 days (Holand, 1997), although (Skinner, 2003) argues that CO₂ blowouts generally could last longer using current blowout control techniques.

1.10.5 Blowout volumes

Based on the estimated blowout rates and statistical blowout durations, blowout volumes can be forecasted, as shown in table. The “Low” case uses the expected blowout rates from the preceding sub-chapters, and a duration of 0.5 days, while the “High” case uses the maximum respective blowout rates and a blowout duration of 5 days.

Released substance	Low case (mean release rate, duration) [m ³]	Worst case (maximum rate, long duration) [m ³]
Oil	74,5	3 090
CH ₄	11 212	463 395

2 EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

This chapter presents possible exposure of CO₂ and CH₄ for defined risk receptors. The leakage magnitude scenarios are based on leakage simulations from abandoned wellbores described in Chapter 1.6, and it is here presumed that all wellbores have been re-abandoned.

2.1 Methodology

A brief overview of the methodology used for the exposure assessment is presented in this chapter. For further model details it is referred to the references provided.

As stated, the starting point for the exposure assessment is probability distributions of CO₂ and CH₄ leakage rates per well. A Monte Carlo simulation framework is used for simulating gas dispersion, and for determining gas concentration at locations for given risk receptors. 10 000 iterations have been used in the Monte Carlo simulation.

For each iteration, a random abandoned well is drawn, and the leakage rate is sampled from this well's leakage rate probability distribution. The dispersion of gas depends in part on local meteorological conditions, in particular wind speed, wind direction and cloudiness. Recent historical meteorological data was obtained² and compiled to establish probability distributions for these parameters, shown in Fig. 2-1, Fig. 2-2 and Fig. 2-3. This data set is based on measurements from the area of interest between 01.06.21 and 11.05.22.

Fig. 2-1: Probability distribution for the wind speed in the area of interest, generated based on recent meteorological data.

² *meteo_condition.xls*

Fig. 2-2: Radar chart for likely wind direction in the area of interest, generated based on recent meteorological data.

Fig. 2-3: Cloud proportion distribution for the area of interest, generated based on recent meteorological data.

The compiled meteorological data shows a mean wind speed of 3,4 m/s, ranging from 0 – 13,9 m/s, most likely wind directions being WNW, NNE and SE, and a mean cloud proportion of 46%.

Gas dispersion is calculated using the Gaussian plume model (Zannetti, 1990) and assuming emission along the centerline of the plume ($y=0$), ground-level emission ($z=0$) and no stack height ($H=0$). The gas concentration at a given point x away from the release point is then given as:

$$c(x, y = 0, z = 0) = \frac{Q}{2\pi u \sigma_y \sigma_z}$$

where

c is gas concentration, g/m³

x is distance from point of release, m

Q is emission (leakage) rate, g/s

σ_y, σ_z are plume standard deviation in lateral/vertical directions

The leakage rate is here converted to mass per time using density of CO₂ or CH₄ at standard conditions, 1,87 kg/m³ and 0,671 kg/m³, respectively. The distance from release point is zero at the abandoned well location and is varied incrementally up to ca. 500 m away. The plume standard deviations, also known as sigma coefficients, are based on semiempirical correlations by Pasquill and Gifford (Gifford, 1961) (Turner, 1970) (Green, Singhal, & Venkateswar, 1980).

The Pasquill-Gifford sigma coefficients require as input a Pasquill dispersion class (ranging from A = Very unstable to G = Very stable), (Pasquill, 1974) (Dobbins, 1979). The Pasquill dispersion class in turn depends on wind speed, day-/nighttime, cloud proportion and insolation.

In the simulations, wind speed is sampled from the distribution shown in Fig. 2-1, day-/nighttime is based on randomly sampling a date and time of day for the current calendar year, cloud proportion is sampled from the distribution shown in Fig. 2-3 and overcast is defined as cloud proportion $\geq 95\%$. Insolation is established based on calculating the solar altitude angle, using as input the randomly sampled date and the latitude of the sampled abandoned wellbore, and using the equations outlined in (Olabi, 2023). Wind direction, sampled based on a discrete distribution using the data in Fig. 2-2, is used to determine the direction of dispersion.

2.2 Risk receptors in area of interest

The term risk receptor is here used to denote humans, animals, vegetation, surface water or infrastructure that could be exposed to elevated levels of CO₂ or CH₄. Risk receptors considered in the further sections are only those entirely or partly located within the defined area of interest (Chapter 1.3). Furthermore, for the purpose of exposure assessment, only humans, animals, vegetation and surface water are considered for relevance.

Tab. 2-1 lists risk receptors that have been considered for the area of interest.

Tab. 2-1: Risk receptors considered for area of interest

Type	Instances
Humans	Žarošice residential area (population: 1100)
	Uhřice residential area (population: 750)
	Archlebov residential area (population: 871)
	Site operators
Animals	Bats
	Birds
	Frogs/Toads
	Lizards
	Otter

Type	Instances
	Bugs
	Polecat
	Butterflies
	Squirrels
Vegetation	Plants
	Flowers
	Trees
Surface water	Vápenka stream
	Zdravá voda
	Klasovsky potok
	Malénský potok
	Spálený potok [west & east]
	Trkmanka
Infrastructure	Roads
	Main/local water supply
	Storage site
	Wastewater plants (4)
	Residential areas

Human populations considered within the area of interest are the Žarošice residential area with a population of ca. 1100, the southern part of Uhřice residential area with a population of ca. 750 and the northern part of Archlebov residential area with a population of ca. 900. In addition, operators at a future storage site are relevant to include in this category, however the precise location of these is not established, and thus exposure assessments for these are therefore performed more qualitative.

Relevant animal species, vegetation, and infrastructure to include have been determined based on CO₂-SPICER Report 1.2 (Janderková, Sedláček, & Krejčí, 2022) and the document *zarosice_protected_species.xls* (Vácha, 2023), which lists species under EU and/or Czech law protection and reported sightings in or around the greater area of interest. A compilation of (Vácha, 2023) is shown for vulnerable species in close proximity (~500 m) to the greater area of interest in Fig. 2-4. For a more detailed listing, see Appendix C.

Fig. 2-4: Number of vulnerable species per Czech red list or law protection status, in or around the greater area of interest.

Note that the classification in the Czech red list and Czech law protection could be the same, similar or different, and columns can therefore not be meaningfully summarized here. The data is based on sightings since 01.01.2000.

For the purpose of the exposure assessment, it is not purposeful to attempt to perform this on a per-species level. Rather, areas defined as nationally protected or nationally important are used as a basis for presumed potential location of all groups of vulnerable species and thus also possible exposure levels. The location of these areas is shown in Fig. 2-5.

Territorial nature protection

- site of European importance (Natura 2000)
- small-scale national specially protected area
- small-scale national specially protected area - buffer zone

Hydrogeology

- hydrological & active water supply vertical well
- safeguard zone of water sources (rank)

- nature park

Species nature protection

- site of nationally important species

Mineral resources

- hydrocarbon field Zar-3 (MND)

Linear infrastructure

- high voltage lines
- ČEPRO petroleum pipeline with 300 m protection zone

Fig. 2-5: Map showing areas that are classified as specially protected or of importance, in or around the area of interest.

The small-scale national specially protected area and sites of nationally important species are entirely or partially within the defined area of interest. The Natura 2000 site of European importance is outside the area of interest and not considered further.

Concerning surface water, there are several ponds in the vicinity of the area of interest. Nový pond, Klášov Pond, Panské ponds, Horní pond, Dolní Dražůvky ponds and Balaton pond are in the greater area, but are outside the area of interest. There are however small streams running through the area of interest; these are: Vápenka stream, Zdravá voda, Klasovský potok, Malénský potok, Spálený potok and Trkmanka.

The main infrastructure in the area of interest consists of buildings (residential, industrial or commercial), roads, water supply and wastewater plants (Žarošice, Dambořice, Uhřice, Ždánice). There are high voltage power lines and a petroleum pipeline, both of which are outside the area of interest. Infrastructure components are not of interest with respect to exposure assessment and are thus only reviewed in terms of effect assessment.

The components of interest for the purpose of exposure assessment are shown in Fig. 2-6.

Fig. 2-6: Map showing area of interest (red) with location of abandoned wellbores (black), residential areas (white), national protected area (magenta), nationally important species regions (orange) and surface water (blue).

The residential areas (white polygons) include only portions confined within the area of interest. The entire Žarošice region is included, while for Uhřice and Archlebov regions only the southern and northern parts are included, respectively.

The following chapter proceeds with a quantitative exposure analysis based on the map in Fig. 2-6.

2.3 Quantitative CO₂ exposure analysis

This chapter presents quantitative assessments of potential exposure levels of CO₂ (CH₄ is addressed briefly in Chapter 2.4), for residential regions Žarošice, Uhřice and Archlebov, for national protected area, and for the three areas of nationally important species. Surface water sources are also included, but are not considered a main point of interest here.

As previously stated, the exposure analysis is based on leakage rate simulations from abandoned wellbores as presented in Chapter 1.6 and based on the methodology outlined in Chapter 2.1. The analysis is stochastic, such that uncertainties both in leakage rate magnitude and in e.g. meteorological conditions impacting dispersion, are preserved and propagated. An important point to note is that gas concentration levels presented are at ground level and based on steady-state leakage. This is a conservative assumption, and unless gas is trapped in a confined space, gas concentration levels are likely lower than those presented here. The gas concentration levels presented are net contributions from release, and thus do not account for existing levels of CO₂ in the atmosphere, which are in the region of 420 ppm and 2 ppm, respectively³.

Fig. 2-7 shows simulated CO₂ ground level concentrations for the area of interest.

Fig. 2-7: Simulated CO₂ ground level concentrations based on leakage from a random abandoned wellbore.

The polygons surrounding the abandoned wellbores represent CO₂ concentrations levels where green = [0-5000 ppm] (yellow = [5000-50000 ppm] and red \geq 50000 ppm are not visible due to no simulations yielding such ranges). As can be observed, there are no polygons intersecting any risk receptors in the area of interest. Exposure to CO₂ levels exceeding 5000 ppm would on this basis only be conceivable in the immediate surrounding of a leaking abandoned wellbore, combined with gas becoming trapped in a confined space. Furthermore, there no simulated scenarios where the specially protected areas are exposed to elevated levels of CO₂.

The largest simulated leakage rates stem from the wells UH9, UH10 and ZA7. Dispersion from these wells have no overlap with any residential areas. A zoomed-in portion of Fig. 2-7 is shown in Fig. 2-8, showing simulated dispersion for wells UH9 and UH10.

³ <https://wmo.int/news/media-centre/greenhouse-gas-concentrations-hit-record-high-again>

are averaged across all simulated directions. Thus, the values here should only be used for indicating relative dispersion importance between abandoned wellbores, and not for indicating likely gas concentration at any given point.

	← Distance from release point [m] →																																															
	10	30	50	70	90	110	130	150	170	190	210	230	250	270	290	310	330	350	370	390	410	430	450	470	490																							
UH9	343.4	36.3	19.7	13.2	9.8	7.7	6.3	5.3	4.6	4.0	3.6	3.2	2.9	2.7	2.5	2.3	2.1	2.0	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.3																							
UH5																																																
UH6																																																
UH9	2071.4	577.3	284.8	190.5	141.3	111.4	91.4	77.2	66.6	58.4	51.9	46.7	42.1	38.6	35.3	32.9	30.5	28.3	26.7	25.1	23.7	22.4	21.2	20.2	19.2																							
UH10	891.5	175.3	94.7	63.3	46.9	37.0	30.4	25.8	22.1	18.4	17.2	15.5	14.0	12.8	11.8	10.9	10.1	9.4	8.8	8.3	7.8	7.4	7.0	6.7	6.4																							
UH11	25.1	6.4	3.4	2.3	1.7	1.3	1.1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2																							
UH12																																																
UH16	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZA1	110.3	28.1	15.2	10.1	7.5	5.9	4.9	4.1	3.5	3.1	2.8	2.5	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.0																							
ZA3	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZA4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZAA4	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZAH1	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZA6	87.9	12.1	6.5	4.4	3.2	2.5	2.1	1.8	1.5	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4																							
ZAA6	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZA7	99.7	99.9	53.8	36.0	26.6	21.0	17.2	14.5	12.5	11.0	9.8	8.8	8.0	7.3	6.7	6.2	5.7	5.3	5.0	4.7	4.4	4.2	4.0	3.8	3.6																							
ZAH1	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZAAH1	0.8	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZAH1																																																
ZAAH1	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
ZA12	23.9	6.1	3.3	2.2	1.6	1.3	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2																							
ZA14H	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																							
Field avg.	191.6	48.7	26.3	17.6	13.0	10.3	8.4	7.1	6.1	5.4	4.8	4.3	3.9	3.6	3.3	3.0	2.8	2.6	2.5	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.0	1.9	1.8																							

Fig. 2-10 Simulated mean downwind CO2 concentration levels (ppm) per abandoned wellbore, across all simulated directions. Color coding is relative to max and min values in this table, not to previous figures.

Fig. 2-10 indicates that wells UH9, UH10 and ZA7 hold a higher dispersion potential relative to all abandoned wellbores.

The field average is generally low, and higher than the 90th percentile of simulations due to UH9 being an outlier. Even at the lowest simulated distance, 10 m from release point, the 90th percentile of simulated CO2 concentration for the field is less than 100 ppm, see Fig. 2-11.

All abandoned wells.: CO2 concentration vs distance from release

Fig. 2-11: Simulated CO2 concentration range (P10-P90 values) across all abandoned wellbores, for increasing distance from point of release. Concentration values are net contribution from release and do not include ambient levels.

For context, the distance from UH9 to the closest point of Žarošice and Uhřice regions is 800 m and 200 m, respectively. Corresponding distances from U10 and ZA7 are 200 m and 1100 m, and 300 m and 1400 m, respectively.

2.4 CH4 exposure assessment

CH4 exposure is addressed in less comprehensive manner than CO2 primarily due to it being of lesser risk from an exposure point of view, however it is included due to it being flammable at levels between 50 000 – 150 000 ppm⁴. Simulations of CH4 dispersions across all abandoned wells shows concentrations far below flammable levels. To reach such levels, gas would have to accumulate through trapping in a confined space (densely vegetated area, inside a structure, or similar) over a sustained period of time.

Fig. 2-12 shows simulated CH4 ground level concentrations for the area of interest.

Fig. 2-12: Simulated CH4 ground level concentrations based on leakage from a random abandoned wellbore.

The polygons surrounding the abandoned wellbores in Fig. 2-12 represent CH4 concentrations levels where green = [0-5000 ppm] and yellow = [5000-50000 ppm] (red \geq 50000 ppm are not visible due to no simulations yielding such ranges). As can be observed, there are no polygons intersecting any risk receptors in the area of interest. Exposure to CH4 levels exceeding 5000 ppm would on this basis only be conceivable in the immediate surrounding of a leaking abandoned wellbore, combined with gas becoming trapped in a confined space. Furthermore, there no simulated scenarios where the specially protected areas are exposed to elevated levels of CH4.

The largest simulated CH4 leakage rates stem from the wells ZA1, UH9 and UH10. Dispersion from these wells have no overlap with any residential areas. A zoomed-in portion

⁴ [https://www1.agric.gov.ab.ca/\\$department/deptdocs.nsf/all/agdex9038/\\$file/729-2.pdf](https://www1.agric.gov.ab.ca/$department/deptdocs.nsf/all/agdex9038/$file/729-2.pdf)

of Fig. 2-12 is shown in Fig. 2-13, showing simulated dispersion for wells ZA1, UH9 and UH10.

Fig. 2-13: Simulated CH₄ ground level concentrations based on leakage from a random abandoned wellbore, shown zoomed in on wells UH9 (west), UH10 (south) and ZA1 (north).

Fig. 2-14: Simulated CH4 concentration range (P10-P90 values) across all abandoned wellbores, for increasing distance from point of release.

Fig. 2-14 shows simulated ground level CH4 concentrations, in terms of 10th and 90th percentiles, across all abandoned wellbores. 10 m from release point, the 90th percentile of simulated CH4 concentration for the field is less than 700 ppm. Only for a case of high release in immediate surroundings of release point, where CH4 was trapped, would it reach potentially flammable levels. It should also be noted that CH4 is lighter than air, and therefore tends to rise. For context, National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health's (NIOSH) maximum recommended safe methane concentration for workers during an 8-hour period is 1 000 ppm⁵.

⁵ [https://www1.agric.gov.ab.ca/\\$department/deptdocs.nsf/all/agdex9038/\\$file/729-2.pdf](https://www1.agric.gov.ab.ca/$department/deptdocs.nsf/all/agdex9038/$file/729-2.pdf)

3 EFFECTS ASSESSMENT

This chapter presents the main results of the effects assessment, beginning with an introduction to CO₂ threshold levels for various receptors, followed by an assessment of potential effects based on these threshold levels in conjunction with leakage scenario presented in Chapters 1.6 (leakage from abandoned wellbores) and exposure assessments presented in Chapter 2.3, for risk receptors defined in Chapter 2.2.

The effects assessment presented assumes exposure to pure CO₂ or CH₄ and does not account for impurities (such as H₂S, SO₂ or NO₂) that could arise from mixing, alteration or mobilization of formation substances.

While there has not been a systematic and comprehensive assessment of how these additional constituents would affect the risks associated with CO₂ storage, it is worth noting that at Weyburn, one of the most carefully monitored CO₂ injection projects and one for which a considerable effort has been devoted to risk assessment, the injected gas contains approximately 2% H₂S (Wilson & Monea, 2005).

3.1 Impact of CO₂ exposure

This chapter presents a brief overview of effects of CO₂ exposure for various groups of risk receptors. The information provided here is used as a basis for establishing some threshold limits for assessing potential effects. However, it should be noted that the threshold levels generally apply to prolonged (> 4 hours) indoor conditions and confined space, while leakage scenarios represent outdoor conditions and non-confined space.

Tab. 3-1: Effects of exposure to CO₂ in indoor air, for humans (Rütters, et al., 2013)

Air CO ₂ concentration [% vol.]	Air CO ₂ concentration [ppm]	Increase against ambient air value [multiplier]	CO ₂ thresholds and effects
0,039	390	---	Global average concentration in ambient air in 2010
0,15	1 500	3,9	Hygienically recommended value for indoors fresh air
0,3	3 000	7,7	MIC value (= maximum indoor concentration), no health concerns to long term exposure below this value
0,5	5 000	12,8	MAC value (= maximum allowable concentration at workplaces)
1,5	15 000	38,5	Breathing rate increases to 40% above the normal level
4	40 000	103	Normal concentration of exhaled air. Weak narcotic effects,

Air CO2 concentration [% vol.]	Air CO2 concentration [ppm]	Increase against ambient air value [multiplier]	CO2 thresholds and effects
			impaired hearing, headache, increased blood pressure and pulse rate
5	50 000	128	Breathing increases to approximately four times the normal rate, symptoms of intoxication become evident, vertigos, slight feeling of choking
8-10	80 000 – 100 000	205 – 256	Very laboured breathing, headache, visual impairment, ringing in the ears, sick, judgment may be impaired, loss of consciousness, exposure of 30-60 minutes leads to death
> 10	> 100 000	> 256	Unconsciousness occurs more rapidly; prolonged exposure may result in death from asphyxiation

Tab. 3-1 refers to possible effects of CO₂ exposure to humans. Plants, insects, and soil organisms have a higher tolerance than humans to elevated CO₂ concentrations. Soil CO₂ levels of about 10 – 20% inhibit root development and decrease water and nutrient uptake, and from 15% concentration there will be effects on terrestrial insects, soil invertebrate, fungi, and microbes become noticeable. However, a low pH and high CO₂ environment may harm others, but favor some species, for example some frogs and other amphibians can often tolerate pH levels as low as 4⁶. CO₂ concentrations above 5% may be dangerous for vegetation and as concentrations approach 20%, CO₂ becomes phytotoxic (Solomon, 2007), see Tab. 3-2.

Tab. 3-2: Effect of CO₂ exposure to plants (IPCC, 2005)

CO ₂ in soil gas [%]	CO ₂ concentration [ppm]	CO ₂ threshold and effect
0,2 – 4	2000 – 40 000	None
> 5	> 50 000	Dangerous
~20	~200 000	Fatal - Phytotoxic

Of plant species, trees are the most resilient, since the roots of trees will be asphyxiated at concentrations exceeding 20% (Damen, Faaji, & Turkenburg, 2006) (Ziogou, et al., 2013).

For animals, these will on average die of asphyxiation at atmospheric CO₂ concentrations above 10%, although this varies with species (Saripalli, Mahasenan, & Cook, 2003). Elevated

⁶ <http://www.fondriest.com/environmental-measurements/parameters/water-quality/ph>

soil CO₂ concentrations may for some species of burrowing animals lead to asphyxiation for concentrations above 8% or lead to chronic disorder of skeletal growth for long-term exposure. Animals may also struggle to adapt in the events of changes to ecosystems and/or food availability (Paulley, Maul, & Metcalfe, 2013). Some studies on CO₂ exposure to animals are available, shown in Tab. 3-3.

Tab. 3-3: Effect of CO₂ exposure on certain animal species (IEA GHG, 2007)

Organism	Amount of CO ₂	Time exposed	Effect
Pig	68%	5 minutes	Death from asphyxia
Rat	6%	24 hours	Cardiac malfunctions in offspring
Unknown	3%	Unknown	Elevated blood pressure and decrease in hearing acuity
Unknown	5%	30 minutes	Signs of intoxication
Unknown	7%	Few minutes	Unconsciousness
Dog	80%	1 minute	Respiratory movement ceased

3.2 Impact of CH₄ exposure

The risks from methane primarily relate to explosive nature due to it being highly flammable, which occurs in the range of 50 000 – 150 000 ppm. Methane is non-toxic when inhaled, but by diluting the oxygen concentration in air below normal levels, it can potentially act as an asphyxiant. According to (Compressed Gas Association, Inc., 2001), using oxygen depletion and for simplicity assuming that CH₄ replaces all O₂, the effects on humans is shown in Tab. 3-4.

Tab. 3-4: Possible effects of oxygen depletion on human health, indirectly indicating effect of CH₄ diluting oxygen

O ₂ level [%]	Approx. CH ₄ concentration* [ppm]	Possible health effect
20,9	~2	Normal – none
19	~20 000	Some unnoticeable adverse physiological effects
16	~50 000	Increased pulse and breathing rate, impaired thinking and attention, reduced coordination

14	~70 000	Abnormal fatigue upon exertion, emotional upset, faulty coordination, poor judgment
12,5	~85 000	Very poor judgment and coordination, impaired respiration that may cause permanent heart damage, nausea, and vomiting
< 10	> ~110 000	Inability to move, loss of consciousness, convulsions, death

3.3 Risk receptor effect analysis

This chapter presents an overview of potential effects of CO₂ and CH₄ exposure, using simulated dispersion scenarios as a basis for exposure levels, and threshold levels as outlined in Chapter 3.1 (CO₂) and 3.2 (CH₄) as guidance for possible effects. The scope here is limited to health effects; economic, operational or other effects are not addressed primarily based on the fact that quantification of such factors is challenging and more importantly that simulated dispersion levels by and large are relatively low and do not in themselves warrant such assessments. The effect assessment is summarized in Tab. 3-5.

Tab. 3-5: Judgment of impact of simulated CO₂/CH₄ exposure, across all leakage scenarios, considering all groups of risk receptors

Leakage scenario [source]	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ leakage rate [m ³ /s]	Risk receptor group ⁷	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ exposure level ⁸ [ppm]	Judgment of impact
Along abandoned wellbores	10 ⁻⁷ – 10 ⁻⁴	Humans (residents/site operators)	0*/~2000	Very low impact. Would require gas becoming trapped/confined and presence of receptors at particular location over prolonged duration, judged as very unlikely to occur. The same is true concerning exposure to operators at storage site though likely closer proximity to release point depending on location of site.
	10 ⁻⁷ – 10 ⁻³		~1700/~5000	
		Animals (protected)	0*/0*	Very low impact. Simulated CO ₂

⁷ For specific instances/species, see Tab. 2-1 and Appendix C

⁸ Based on simulated dispersion, see Chapter 2.3. Zero should be interpreted as ambient air concentration levels.

Leakage scenario [source]	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ leakage rate [m ³ /s]	Risk receptor group ⁷	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ exposure level ⁸ [ppm]	Judgment of impact
		Animals (other)	~50/~150	<p>concentration does not intersect specially protected areas. This does obviously not exclude possibility of exposure to singular/plural instances, but prolonged exposure would have to occur in close proximity to well.</p> <p>Low impact. Possible exposure levels strongly depend on both location of receptor, location of habitat, and exposure is generally less likely where release points are close to residential/urban areas than for more remote locations.</p>
		Vegetation (protected) Vegetation (other)	0*/0* ~1700/5 000	<p>Very low impact. Simulated CO₂ concentration does not intersect specially protected areas</p> <p>Low impact. For case of high leakage rate, vegetation in immediate surrounding would likely be impacted, but limited to distance from release point of ~10m.</p>
		Surface water	N/A	Very low impact. Only Vápenka stream in close enough proximity to be of relevant, but release to surface unlikely to have any impact on water pH levels
		Infrastructure (site) Infrastructure (other)	~1700/5 000 0*/0*	Very low impact. Main risk stems from flammable CH ₄ accumulating due to trapping for sustained period until reaching explosive thresholds without detection.

Leakage scenario [source]	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ leakage rate [m ³ /s]	Risk receptor group ⁷	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ exposure level ⁸ [ppm]	Judgment of impact
Through caprock	10 ⁻¹³ – 10 ⁻¹⁰	All	0*/0*	Very low impact. Only relevant where migrated CO ₂ /CH ₄ would accumulate over prolonged period in soil or confined pockets, which would have a very small impact on animals/vegetation/water. No expected impact on humans/infrastructure as caprock does not intersect with residential/urban areas.
Along faults	N/A	All	0*/0*	No impact. Absence of clearly definable faults in the area of the Zar-3 structure
From spill points	10 ⁻⁶ – 10 ⁻⁵	All	~30/~150	Very low impact. Magnitude based on migration towards either UH5 or U11 followed by leakage through these well barriers. Simulated dispersion and possible exposure from these wells are, due to both leakage potential and proximity to risk receptors, considered very low.
Blowout from injection or monitoring well	~10 ⁻¹	Risk receptors beyond immediate vicinity of release	5000 – 10 000	Moderate to severe impact, strongly depending on both type of release (oil/gas/CO ₂), location and magnitude and time to kill blowout.

3.4 Effects of impurities

Impurities in dispersed gas, either from impurities in injected CO₂, or as a naturally occurring compound in hydrocarbon gas, could be released as part of the identified leakage scenarios. Impurities could include SO₂, NO_x, CO, H₂S, He, N₂, O₂, Ar, Hg, As, Se, and other trace elements. Such elements, given specific conditions or concentrations, could pose toxicity- or acidic-related risks. Acidic substances could potentially degrade well barriers by corrosion. Toxic substances would pose a health risk given sufficiently large exposure and duration. Monitoring measures, such as listed in Tab. 4-3, are thus important also as early warning

systems for detecting such substances, as these would potentially only be contained in mixture with CO₂ or CH₄. While a full assessment similar to CO₂ or CH₄ for impurities is beyond the scope of this report, a simplified assessment is here presented for H₂S, considered the worst-case impurity from an effects impact perspective.

H₂S, or hydrogen sulfide, is a highly flammable, explosive gas that can pose danger to human health at high concentrations. According to the US Department of Labor's Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), H₂S concentration levels <5 ppm could cause minor symptoms, whereas 20-100 ppm would yield moderate symptoms and >100 ppm are dangerous or fatal⁹. Assuming a conservative 2% H₂S content released as part of CH₄ dispersion, and a mean leakage rate for CH₄ in the region of 10⁻⁵ m³/s, would yield possible concentration levels in the region < 5 ppm of H₂S using similar models and assumptions as described in Chapter 2.1. Concentration levels >5 ppm are possible in the event of higher H₂S concentration, higher leakage rate, wind-still conditions combined with gas trapping in confined spaces.

4 RISK CHARACTERIZATION

This chapter summarizes the main results from the previous chapters and provides an overall assessment of the main storage risks. It is important to note all relevant assumptions and sources of uncertainty stated in Chapters 1-3, although a listing is provided also here. Where possible, the previous assessments have tried to quantify and propagate uncertainties to the extent possible.

4.1 Assessment of likelihood of occurrence

Assessing likelihood of occurrence for leakage scenarios is challenging when considering a very long time scale. While there are some existing analogous frequencies that could be used as reference, these are not necessarily directly applicable to the storage site in question, as site-specific factors will differ. Caution is therefore advised in placing too much emphasis on use of the frequencies listed here. They are provided as references levels for contextualization of relative likelihood between different leakage scenarios first and foremost.

Concerning abandoned wells there are varying sources regarding frequencies for estimating likelihood of leakage. One study indicated a long-term (>~10 000 years) failure probability of a low-rate leakage to be in the order of magnitude of 10⁻³ per abandoned well, and 10⁻³-10⁻⁴ for active (injection or monitoring) wells (LeGuen, Meyer, Poupard, Houdu, & Chammas, 2009). Probabilities for a blowout occurring depend to a large degree on region and prevailing safety cultures, regulations and specific conditions; based on offshore wells worldwide could suggest possible ranges (considering well intervention activities) between 10⁻⁴-10⁻⁶ (Randhol & Carlsen, 2008).

Observations from engineered and natural analogues as well as models suggest that the fraction of CO₂ retained in appropriately selected and managed geological reservoirs is very likely to exceed 99% over 100 years and is likely to exceed 99% over 1,000 years (IPCC, 2005). One related analogue is from natural gas storage for which the UK Health and Safety Executive have assessed the failure rate for a geological failure of the storage cavity in an Underground gas storage facility to be of the order of 10⁻⁵ failures per well year, or 1 in 100,000 chance of failure per well per year of operation (British Geological Survey, 2008).

⁹ <https://www.osha.gov/hydrogen-sulfide/hazards>

4.2 Overall evaluation

Summary of leakage scenarios, coded with reference numbers used in the subsequent risk matrix is provided in Tab. 4-1.

Tab. 4-1: Reference numbers for leakage scenarios considering and used in risk matrix

Reference number	Leakage scenario
1.1	Leakage of CO ₂ from abandoned wellbore
1.2	Leakage of CO ₂ through caprock
1.3	Leakage of CO ₂ along faults
1.4	Leakage of CO ₂ from spill points
2.1	Leakage of CH ₄ from abandoned wellbore
2.2	Leakage of CH ₄ through caprock
2.3	Leakage of CH ₄ along faults
2.4	Leakage of CH ₄ from spill points
3.1	Blowout from monitoring or injection well

The leakage scenarios listed in Tab. 4-1 are mapped in a risk matrix shown in Tab. 4-2, combining judged likelihood of occurrence and possible consequences (covering health and safety, operational impact and environmental impact).

Tab. 4-2: Risk matrix indicating potential likelihood of occurrence and consequence, for identified leakage scenarios of the storage phase

Consequence			1 - Insignificant	2 - Minor	3 - Moderate	4 - Major	5 - Catastrophic
		Safety	Medical treatment, minor health effects, first aid case, or less	Medical treatment with restricted duty or medium health effects	One or more lost time workday cases or significant medical treatment	Permanent disability, multiple hospitalizations, or major health effects	Fatality, Public hospitalization, or severe health effects
		Operational	0-10M USD	10-100M USD	100M-1MM USD	1-10MM USD	> 10MM USD
		Environmental	Small scale and short recovery time	Large scale and short recovery time	Short scale and long recovery time	Large scale and long recovery time	Large scale and long-lasting effect or permanent damage
Probability							
1	Improbable	< 10 ⁻⁶					
2	Remote	10 ⁻⁶ – 10 ⁻⁴					

4.3 Risk-reducing measures

The following table presents risk-reducing measures proposed based on the risk assessment. The measures may be preventive (reducing the likelihood that leakage will occur) or mitigating (reducing the impact of the leakage). This is meant as input to a decision-making process of the planning/design stages of the storage site. The table is not exhaustive; other relevant measures, both related and non-related to risk, should also be considered.

Tab. 4-3: List of selected risk-reducing measures for consideration

Leakage scenario	Type of measure	Category	Remarks
Abandoned wellbores	Re-abandonment of all wells in accordance with prevailing standards/regulations	Preventive	Mandatory. Improvement of P&A design directly lowers leakage potential from abandoned wellbores.
	Evaluate possibility of using chemically resistant cement (CO ₂ , brine, H ₂ S)	Preventive	Opportunity to provide increased reliability in long-term sealability
	Intermittent soil gas and/or atmospheric gas monitoring around wellbores	Mitigating	Area around wells UH9, UH10, ZA7 are candidate wells based on risk evaluations. Can be evaluated relative to monitoring measurements presented in Chapter 1.6.10. Should be performed at regular intervals (e.g. annually)
	Sonic well logging	Mitigating	Sonic logging of monitoring well to determine

Leakage scenario	Type of measure	Category	Remarks
			non-sealing cement and tubing
	Wireline logging	Mitigating	Wireline logging at the injection wells and monitoring wells can indicate unconformities in well integrity
	Wellhead pressure/temperature measurement	Preventive	Sensors in injection wells may be early detection of loss of well integrity
	Downhole pressure/temperature measurement	Mitigating	Downhole sensors in monitoring wells can reveal anomalies/symptoms of leakage.
	Repair or re-abandonment in the event of detected leaking wellbores	Mitigating	Use of standard recompletion techniques, remedial chemical or mechanical techniques for plugging defect cement barriers
Leakage through caprock	Install ground observations during re-injection phase	Mitigating	Indications of vertical fracture propagation in overburden by monitoring and potentially be used to generate any early warning signal that can be used during operation (vary injection pressure, volume, induce waiting time to allow for equilibration of the reservoir, etc)
Blowout from injection or monitoring well	Well kill mechanisms contingency plan	Mitigating	Relevant only in the event of loss of well control. Use of heavy mud for bullheading or casing perforation/squeeze cementing where wellhead accessible or drilling of relief well when this is not the case.
All	Injected volume, and injection pressure/temperature to respect safe limits as per Chapter 1.7.4.	Preventive	Mandatory. Setting operational parameters must be determined based on careful evaluations of cost/benefit and acceptable level of risk.

Leakage scenario	Type of measure	Category	Remarks
	Lower injection pressure by injecting at lower rate or through multiple wells	Preventive	

4.4 Sources of uncertainty

This chapter presents some of the most important uncertainties, pertaining to all results and evaluations presented in this chapter. The list is not exhaustive and does not address specific inherent uncertainties in models used throughout – for these uncertainties it is referred to the source documents where these are further elaborated.

- The true state of well barriers of abandoned wells is not known. The models used to estimate leakage rates are based on assumed defect size of cemented barriers. The defect is assumed conservative; however the possibility of greater defect sizes cannot be entirely excluded (yielding higher leakage rates). The defect size could also be affected in terms of exposure of cement to acidic components over time. Leakage on the outside of the casing (not included in leakage simulations) is also a possible scenario, although the leakage magnitude for such a scenario would likely be in the same order of magnitude as those assessed.
- Simulated results also strongly depend on prevailing reservoir pressure. While this is to some extent governed by decision on injection rate and volume, and has been conservatively assumed with a wide range here, there is uncertainty in terms of at which points and over which time pressure build-up will occur.
- The final re-abandonment well barrier design was not available at the time of assessment, and as such are based on assumed design. The impact of this assumption could impact leakage magnitude, although not in an extensive manner.
- Blowout simulations consider a two-phase blowout of oil and hydrocarbon gas; blowout of CO₂ or hydrocarbon gas only could potentially yield greater rates than those indicated in this report. The presumed input parameters to the blowout assessment were also associated with greater uncertainties (such as permeability) than for all other leakage scenarios, and thus should be used with far greater caution.
- Likelihood (probability) of occurrence is extremely challenging to quantify for a field-specific case; those listed in this report are only meant as comparable reference cases. However, there are no factors specific for the area of interest that would indicate significant differences for analogous or comparable cases, one way or the other.
- The exact location of the injected CO₂ plume is not known, for the purpose of the assessments it is assumed within the reservoir confinements as planned, and exposure and effect (of CO₂) is judged on this basis.
- The degree of impurities, either in the injected CO₂ or in the hydrocarbon gas, is the former case not known and in the latter case was not available at the time of assessment. Only coarse assessments of H₂S have been considered, while acidic substances have not been considered.

- Factors that influence the geomechanical stability assessment include uncertainties related to earth stresses, stiffness parameters, as well as inherent variability in results obtained from laboratory analyses
- The permeability of the sealing formations is assumed to be similar to core sample measurements used from seals from Mikulov Fm. and Zarosice Mb, although the exact degree to which these are fully representative is not determined.
- Zar-3 field erosional boundary varies slightly from one interpretation to another, due to poor resolution of the seismic and lack of wells for detailed correlations
- The Vranovice formation is formed by more or less isolated bodies of dolomites and limestones. Based on the available seismic and well data, it is not possible to say for certain whether the carbonate body of Zar-3 field is connected to other bodies to the northwest and east or is isolated from one of them
- Simulated gas dispersions is based on recent local meteorological data, however there is an uncertainty in how future (in particular, long-term) weather conditions may change, due to e.g. climate changes.
- It must be kept in mind that the scope of this report covers only the area of interest. Concerns or impacts beyond the area of interest boundaries are not considered.

4.5 Summary

This report comprises assessments of risks primarily relating to long-term storage of CO₂ for the Zar-3 field, limited to the area of interest as defined in Chapter 1.3, and risks are here those concerning compromised storage integrity due to leak of CO₂ and/or natural gas (CH₄), that could, under specific conditions deviating from planned and expected behavior, escape from the storage confinements. The leakage scenarios, covering the injection and long-term storage phases, include leakage from abandoned wellbores, through the caprock formations, along faults or spill points or from injection or monitoring wells, as defined in Chapter 1.5. The identified leakage scenarios do not cover absolutely all possible scenarios, but represent the most relevant risks based on evaluations of site-specific characteristics and published literature, studies and experience from analogous storage sites. Risks relating to security of the operating site (such as intentional threats, sabotage, etc.), workplace hazards or rare extreme natural disasters or weather conditions are beyond the scope of this assessment and must be separately assessed as part of planning and design of the injection site. In all assessments covered in this report it has been assumed that injection and storage operations and conditions are aligned with existing laws, regulations and standards wherever applicable.

The risk assessments have to the extent possible been based on use of quantitative risks analyses combined with stochastic frameworks as a means to better communicate risks, compare risks relatively and not least to identify, propagate and communicate uncertainties. The results of quantitative, as well as qualitative risk assessments should always consider stated assumptions and limitations that govern these assessments. Leakage simulations from abandoned wellbores, through caprock and from injection/monitoring wells (Chapters 1.6, 1.7 and 1.10) and judgements of faults and spill points (Chapters 1.8 and 1.9) are accompanied by surveys conducted in terms of re-logging of well ZA7 (Chapter 1.6.9) and soil gas monitoring around wellbores (Chapter 1.6.10).

The consequences of the leakage scenarios are considered for risk receptors of the area of interest, i.e. humans (future site operators and residential areas), animals, vegetation, surface

water and infrastructure, as detailed in Chapter 2.2. Simulations of gas dispersion from abandoned wellbores (Chapter 2.3) have been performed to determine possible gas concentration levels at various proximities based on likely locations of risk receptors. These results were then compared with relevant exposure threshold levels (Chapters 3.1-3.2) to determine possible impacts of exposure (Chapter 3.3), including brief considerations of impurities in dispersed gas (Chapter 3.4). Judgements of likelihood of occurrence, although not specifically related to the storage site but based on available literature, were provided in Chapter 4.1. Evaluations of possible risk reducing measures, covering both preventive (probability-reducing) and mitigating (consequence-reducing) measures and key uncertainties of the assessments in this report were provided in Chapters 4.3 and 4.4, respectively.

As an important note, this report should be considered in conjunction with related work package reports of the CO₂-SPICER project, including but not limited to 3D geological modelling (WP2), dynamic modelling and simulations (WP3), geomechanical assessments (WP4), geochemistry of rocks and fluids (WP5), monitoring (WP7) and scenarios of future site development (WP8), all of which complement information and/or findings presented here.

Some of the key findings in this report are summarized below.

- All leakage scenarios assessed are viewed to have a low likelihood of occurrence.
 - In relative terms, leakage from abandoned wells has a higher likelihood of occurrence than other assessed scenarios. As such, this scenario should have a higher priority with respect to implementation of risk-reducing measures.
 - In relative terms, a blowout from an injection or monitoring well has a far greater impact potential relative to all other assessed scenarios. As such, this scenario should have a higher priority with respect to implementation of risk-reducing measures.
- Simulations of leakage from abandoned wellbores suggest potential leakage rates in the order of magnitude of $10^{-7} - 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (CO₂ or CH₄). For a blowout, possible gas rates would be several orders of magnitude greater, and represent a sudden, rapid release as opposed to a slow seepage.
 - The largest simulated CO₂ leakage rates from abandoned wellbores are from the wells UH9, UH10 and ZA7
- The most important correlating factors between abandoned wellbore characteristics and corresponding leakage magnitude are quality of cemented well barriers, length of cemented well barriers and prevailing reservoir pressure.
- The effect of re-abandonment would for most wells lower both the potential for a leakage occurring as well as any possible impact, judged based on assumed re-abandonment design to lower leakage magnitude by approximately 60-70% on average.
- Results both from re-logging of well ZA7 and soil gas monitoring around wellbores indicate that the current wellbore integrity of the Zar-3 wells is proper, with no indications of either defect cement zones or elevated detections of methane, respectively.
- The leakage magnitude, based on core samples of caprock permeability and thickness maps for Mikulov and Paleogene formations, are believed to be several orders of magnitude lower than leakage from abandoned wellbores.
- Data shows that the overburden rocks are much stronger than the reservoir (both tensile strength, frictional coefficient and cohesion). The 'effective' stresses in the overburden,

with nearly zero porosity and sub-nanoscale permeability, will not be affected by any pore pressure variation in the reservoir.

- The injected CO₂ amounts are inadequate to reduce the temperature in the overburden, and rock-fluid interactions in the overburden are limited by the transport of any potentially chemically reactive elements due to its negligible permeability.
- The only failure scenario of the overburden is if reservoir ballooning/swelling reduces side stress of the overburden rock until they become negative, then vertically oriented hydraulic fractures will grow if the extensive stress exceeds the tensile strength. This scenario is deemed very unlikely, also since no reservoir subsidence nor overburden compaction effects have been observed during the production phase of the field.
- Based on Monte Carlo simulations of geomechanical failure, safe re-pressurization is in the region of 19-20 MPa, or higher (21-22 MPa), depending on assumed state of formations.
- The nearest fault identified is located in the aquifer at large distance from the hydrocarbon field. CO₂ injection is planned to be carried out in the field area and impact of the pilot injection addressed in this project on overall pressure build-up in the aquifer is assumed to be limited, however the effect of the pressure build-up and fault leakage potential should be further evaluated.
- In the case of leakage of stored CO₂ through a spill-point, the most likely migration paths are either northwest to the well UH11 area or east to northeast to the well area UH5, or in both directions, depending on the isolation degree of the reservoir body from its surroundings.
- The compiled meteorological data shows a mean wind speed of 3,4 m/s, ranging from 0 – 13,9 m/s, most likely wind directions being WNW, NNE and SE, and a mean cloud proportion of 46%.
- The main risk receptors of interest with respect to exposure assessment are humans (site operators, residential areas of Žarošice, Uhřice and Archlebov) and protected species (animals/vegetation). The distance from well UH9 to the closest point of Žarošice and Uhřice regions is 800 m and 200 m, respectively. Corresponding distances from U10 and ZA7 are 200 m and 1100 m, and 300 m and 1400 m, respectively.
- Based on available literature, threshold levels of CO₂ concentration with regards to human health suggests intervals of < 5000 ppm yielding low impact, 5000 – 50 000 ppm yielding moderate impact, and > 50 000 yielding serious impact on human health. Corresponding thresholds for CH₄ are generally higher, the main risks of CH₄ concentrations being dilution of oxygen, and it being flammable/explosive (50 000 – 150 000 ppm). Plants, insects, and soil organisms have a higher tolerance than humans to elevated CO₂ concentrations.
 - While impurities were not analyzed to the full extent, H₂S, a toxic substance, could, for concentration levels <5 ppm could cause minor symptoms, whereas 20-100 ppm would yield moderate symptoms and >100 ppm are dangerous or fatal.
- Simulations of gas dispersion from abandoned wellbores do not intersect any risk receptors in the area of interest. Exposure to CO₂ levels exceeding 5000 ppm would on this basis only be conceivable in the immediate surrounding of a leaking abandoned wellbore, combined with gas becoming trapped in a confined space. Furthermore, there

no simulated scenarios where the specially protected areas are exposed to elevated levels of CO₂.

- Surface water streams have no overlapping areas with simulated CO₂ dispersion from abandoned wellbores, and even in the event that this was the case, the gas (release to surface) would have to mix with water to alter the pH in any way.
- Simulations of dispersed CO₂ from abandoned wellbores, 10 m from release point, suggest that 90th percentile of simulated CO₂ ground level concentration (net contribution from leakage) across all abandoned wellbores is less than 100 ppm.
- Simulations of CH₄ dispersions across all abandoned wells shows concentrations far below flammable levels (50 000 – 150 000 ppm). To reach such levels, gas would have to accumulate through trapping in a confined space (densely vegetated area, inside a structure, or similar) over a sustained period of time.
- As for CO₂, simulations of CH₄ dispersion from abandoned wellbores do not intersect any risk receptors in the area of interest. Simulated ground level CH₄ concentrations, 10 m from release point, the 90th percentile of simulated CH₄ concentration for the field is less than 700 ppm.
- Overall, both CO₂ and CH₄ likely exposure would have a very low impact and would require gas becoming trapped/confined and presence of receptors at particular location over prolonged duration, judged as very unlikely to occur. The same is true concerning exposure to operators at storage site, although likely closer proximity to release point depending on location of site. At close proximity to release from abandoned wellbores, simulated concentrations could reach 2000 ppm (CO₂)/5000 ppm (CH₄).
- Meteorological conditions have a meaningful impact on simulated gas dispersion results, where in general the worst conditions in this context are combination of low wind speeds (< 2 m/s) combined with night-time (no insolation).
- Assuming a conservative 2% H₂S content released as part of CH₄ dispersion, and a mean leakage rate for CH₄ in the region of 10⁻⁵ m³/s, would yield possible concentration levels in the region < 5 ppm of H₂S. Concentration levels >5 ppm could be possible in the event of higher H₂S concentration, higher leakage rate, wind-still conditions combined with gas trapping in confined spaces.
- Likelihood of occurrence for defined leakage scenarios have not been specifically assessed for the storage site, however statistics/literature/analogous sites/storage types suggest frequencies of leakage from abandoned wellbores, in terms of occurrence per operating year, in the range of 10⁻³-10⁻⁴ and other scenarios at least 1-2 orders of magnitude below this range. Caution is however advised against placing too much emphasis on such numbers; they are mostly useful in terms of relative comparisons.
- Risk-reducing measures have been suggested, and it is recommended to consider using an ALARP (As Low As Reasonably Practicable) principle for implementation of these. Measures include:
 - Well design measures, including mandatory re-abandonment of all wellbores and evaluating use of chemically resistant cement alternatives to standard Portland class G cement
 - Intermittent monitoring of soil gas and comparisons versus baseline measurements

- Sonic, wireline and downhole/wellhead pressure/temperature monitoring
 - Well repair where required
 - Ground observations during injection, for detection of anomalies of overburden integrity
 - Appropriate well kill mechanisms and contingency plans, dimensioned for possible leak rates. It is here recommended that more accurate and in-depth assessments of blowout potential be performed in relation to this.
 - Operational parameters, specifically injected volume, and injection pressure/temperature, to respect safe re-pressurization limits in accordance with geomechanical risk assessments.
 - Perform in-depth assessments of various injection scenarios for different operating parameters, and including injection from multiple wells, in order to optimize long-term storage integrity.
- Some of the key uncertainties, relating to results presented in this report and/or the storage integrity in general, include:
 - The true state of well barriers, current and future, are not known, but assessed to the extent possible.
 - Final abandonment designs for the wellbores have been assumed and might differ from actual design.
 - Blowout assessments are only indicative and limited to oil/gas two-phase blowout. Single phase gas or CO₂ blowouts could potentially yield higher rates than those indicated here.
 - Scenarios not covered, and/or risks beyond the area of interest, represent uncertainties that could still be relevant to further assessment, depending on factors influencing key decisions of the site planning stage.

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Appendix A: Well schematics

The following sections provides schematics of all wells included in the WP6 analysis. This included basic information (location, year drilled, measured depth), lithology and well design. It also includes an indication of assumed vertical migration pathway (starting point, exit point, and which barriers are considered breached)

Fig. A-1: Well schematic for UH3.

Fig. A-2: Well schematic for UH5.

Fig. A-3: Well schematic for UH6.

Fig. A-4: Well schematic for UH9.

Fig. A-5: Well schematic for UH10.

Fig. A-6: Well schematic for UH11.

Fig. A-7: Well schematic for UH12.

Fig. A-8: Well schematic for UH16.

Fig. A-9: Well schematic for ZA1.

Fig. A-10: Well schematic for ZA3.

Fig. A-11: Well schematic for ZA4.

Fig. A-12: Well schematic for ZA4A.

Fig. A-13: Well schematic for ZA5H.

Fig. A-14: Well schematic for ZA6.

Fig. A-15: Well schematic for ZA6A.

Fig. A-16: Well schematic for ZA7.

Fig. A-17: Well schematic for ZA8H.

Fig. A-18: Well schematic for ZA8AH.

Fig. A-19 Well: schematic for ZA9H.

Fig. A-20: Well schematic for ZA9AH.

Fig. A-21: Well schematic for ZA12.

Fig. A-21: Well schematic for ZA14H.

Appendix B: Geochemistry, mud logs and mineralogy

Geochemical properties of the caprocks are among the key elements in the assessment of the risk of possible CO₂ leakage from the planned storage (depleted oil and gas reservoir). Mud logs, i.e. data obtained during the drilling of exploration and production wells provide important basis for the analysis of potential leakage paths through the caprocks. Here we present mud logs results together with associated well log measurements, laboratory analyses of cores and cuttings, well tests results, chromatographic analyses of liquid and gaseous media. The intention is to interpret all the data in the context of the 3D model of the geological structure in the area of interest.

In the first phase, ČGS in cooperation with MND generated a database of the mud log and well log data converted into LAS and suitable formats applicable in several program types (Fig. B-1).

Fig. B-1: Well ZA3 – scheme of conversion of mudlog data into a standard .las format – fluorescence (luminescence).

Examples of the conversion of mudlog data into a standard .las format and their presentation in geological profiles, maps or in 3D visualization are shown in Fig. B-1, B-2 and B-3.

Correlations of parameters on individual wells, especially trip gas, direct and enhanced luminescence, allow monitoring of hydrocarbon shows in caprocks and their sealing properties in the vicinity of the oil and gas reservoir. Rate of penetration, rotary speed and weight on bit can contribute to understanding of the mechanical properties of rocks.

Fig. B-2: Well ZA7 – selected parameters from mudlog measurements in standard .las format. Explanations: rate of penetration (min./m) – ROPa, rate of penetration (m/h) – ROPb, weight on bit (t) – WOB, standpipe pressure (barr) – SPP, trip gas (%) – T GAS direct luminescence (0.5 – 3 level) – P, luminescence enhanced by DCM (0.5 – 3 level) – N.

Fig. B-3: Uninterpreted N-S cross section of ZAR-3 oil and gas field with luminescence logs in .las format of the ZA6, ZA6A, ZA3, ZA4A, ZA4 wells.

The difference between the correlation of parameters on the original mudlog records and the .las formats is evident from Fig. B-4 and B-5. It is especially important for directional and horizontal wells.

Fig. B-4: N-S correlation scheme of the Zar-3 oil and gas field with luminescence logs in the ZA6, ZA6A, ZA3, ZA4A, ZA4 wells - original output from mud log. Red horizontal columns show oily substances under UV light, blue columns show the same but after organic solvent, which makes the enhanced luminescence.

The luminescence under UV illumination is registered either as direct secondary light of the sampled cuttings (Fig. B-4 red horizontal columns) or enhanced luminescence (blue columns) after spraying organic solvent (e.g. DCM) on the cuttings, which acts as extraction agent of hydrocarbon compounds from the rocks.

The mud logs indicate the strongest signal of petroleum hydrocarbon shows in several intervals within the reservoir. Second strongest shows are registered in the immediate vicinity of the reservoir, especially in the Paleogene rocks of the Nesvacilka Fm (Fig. B-4 and B-5), weaker shows are found in the underlying Lower Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. Similar features were observed numerous oil and gas fields in the southern Moravia (Czech Republic). Luminescence signals are almost absent in the Upper Jurassic Mikulov Fm., which seems to be a more efficient seal. Almost no luminescence signal is registered in the overthrust Zdanice unit (Carpathian Flysch Belt). It is interpreted as the most important seal (no. 3) in the storage complex (Fig. B-4 and B-5).

Fig. B-5: Interpreted N-S cross section of ZAR-3 oil and gas field with luminescence logs in .las format in the ZA6, ZA6A, ZA3, ZA4A, ZA4 wells.

Complementary information is provided by the gaseous hydrocarbons within the mudlog measurements. Some trip gas occurs in some wells in the secondary caprock, i.e. the Nemcice Fm. (Fig. B-6) above the overthrust plane.

Fig. B-6: Oriented well ZA5H with well logs showing rate of penetration and trip gas.

In Figs. B-7 to B-9 the luminescence of petroleum hydrocarbons and trip gas are shown as they appear within and above the reservoir. It is noteworthy that even in the underlying silty sandstone of the Myslejovice Fm. oil and gas shows are observed.

Fig. B-7: Schematic 3D view - occurrences of direct (A) and enhanced luminescence (B) at all stratigraphic levels of the Zar-3 oil and gas field.

Fig. B-8: Schematic 3D view – occurrences of direct (A) and enhanced (B) luminescence above the top of the Vranovice Fm. reservoir.

Fig. B-9: Schematic 3D view – occurrences of direct (A) and enhanced fluorescence (B) above the base of the Nemcice Fm. (thrust plane of the Carpathian Flysch belt).

Fig. B-10: Schematic 3D view – (A) occurrences of trip gas at all stratigraphic levels of the Zar-3 oil and gas field, (B) above the top of the Vranovice Fm., and (C) above the base of the Nemcice Fm., thrust plane of the Zdanice unit (Carpathian Flysch Belt).

The luminescence and trip gas indications are not interpreted as evidence of poor seal and direct oil and gas leaks from the Zar-3 field, but rather as zones with traces of regional long-term oil and gas migration in course of geological history of the past 17 mil. years. The above data show the sensitivity of the mudlogging, which is able to detect also “non-movable” hydrocarbons in low permeability rocks.

Current geochemical investigations complement the mud log data with molecular characteristics. The preliminary results show, that a number of Paleogene caprock samples contain hydrocarbons of the same origin as the principal Zar-3 oil accumulation. Yet, a few samples were found with low permeability in the Paleogene caprock interval, which contain the original syngenetic bitumen of very low thermal maturity, very different from the thermally mature oil in the reservoir. More information is being prepared for the final version of the risk report.

Appendix C: Species under EU or Czech law protection

Tab. C-1: Species under EU or Czech law protection, sightings within 500 m of center of greater area of interest, since 01.01.2000

Category	Species	Species [CZ]	Czech law protection	Czech red listing	Last sighting
Amphibians	Bufo bufo	ropucha obecná	O	VU	2021-04
	Bufo viridis	ropucha zelená	SO	EN	2015-04
	Pelophylax esculentus s. l.	skokan zelený komplex	SO	NT	2011-04
	Rana dalmatina	skokan štíhlý	SO	NT	2011-04
Bats	Myotis myotis	netopýr velký	KO	NT	2004-12
	Plecotus austriacus	netopýr dlouhouchý	SO	VU	2004-12
Birds	Accipiter nisus	krahujec obecný	SO	VU	2017-02
	Apus apus	rorýs obecný	O		2022-07
	Ardea alba	volavka bílá	SO		2020-02
	Circus aeruginosus	moták pochop	O	VU	2023-05
	Circus cyaneus	moták pilich	SO	CR	2011-04
	Circus pygargus	moták lužní	SO	EN	2021-06
	Coloeus monedula	kavka obecná	SO	NT	2014-03
	Columba oenas	holub doupňák	SO	VU	2017-04
	Corvus corax	krkavec velký	O		2017-02
	Coturnix coturnix	křepelka polní	SO	NT	2018-05
	Dendrocopos syriacus	strakapoud jižní	SO	EN	2020-12
	Dryocopus martius	datel černý			2017-02
	Falco columbarius	ďřemlík tundrový	SO		2012-12
	Falco peregrinus	sokol stěhovavý	KO	EN	2020-12
	Gallinago gallinago	bekasina otavní	SO	EN	2022-04
	Hirundo rustica	vlaštovka obecná	O	NT	2021-05
	Jynx torquilla	krutihlav obecný	SO	VU	2019-05
	Lanius collurio	řuhák obecný	O	NT	2021-05
	Lanius excubitor	řuhák šedý	O	VU	2020-12
	Luscinia megarhynchos	slavík obecný	O		2022-04
Merops apiaster	víha pestrá	SO	EN	2019-08	
Milvus milvus	luňák červený	KO	CR	2022-04	

Category	Species	Species [CZ]	Czech law protection	Czech red listing	Last sighting
	Motacilla flava	konipas luční	SO	VU	2022-04
	Oriolus oriolus	žluva hajní	SO		2016-06
	Tringa glareola	vodouš bahenní			2022-04
	Tringa totanus	vodouš rudonohý	KO	CR	2022-04
	Upupa epops	dudek chocholatý	SO	EN	2022-04
Bugs	Brachinus expulso	prskavec menší	O		2020-05
	Carabus scheidleri	střevlík Scheidlerův	O		2020-07
	Carabus ulrichii	střevlík Ulrichův	O		2020-07
	Cicindela campestris	svižník polní	O		2011-05
	Lucanus cervus	roháč obecný	O	VU	2022-08
	Oxythyrea funesta	zlatohlávek tmavý	O		2020-05
	Tropinota hirta	zlatohlávek huňatý	SO	VU	2020-05
Butterflies	Iphiclides podalirius	otakárek ovocný	O	NT	2022-07
	Lycaena dispar	ohniváček černočerný	SO		2022-07
	Saturnia pyri	martináč hrušňový	SO	NT	2017-05
Mammals	Lutra lutra	vydra říční	SO	NT	2015-10
	Mustela putorius	tchoř tmavý		DD	2023-09
	Sciurus vulgaris	veverka obecná	O	DD	2019-08
Other insects	Tibicina haematodes	cikáda viničná	KO	CR	2020-06
Plants	Adonis vernalis	hlaváček jarní	O	VU	2020-09
	Anemone sylvestris	sasanka lesní	O	EN	2008-05
	Aster amellus subsp. bessarabicus	hvězdnice chlumní velkoúborná	O	NT	2020-09
	Astragalus austriacus	kozinec rakouský	SO	NT	2012-07
	Cephalanthera damasonium	okrotice bílá	O	NT	2023-05
	Cornus mas	dřín jarní	O		2008-05
	Epipactis palustris	kruštík bahenní	SO	VU	2022-06
	Galanthus nivalis	sněženka podsněžník	O	NT	2020-09
	Gentiana cruciata	hořec křížatý	O	EN	2021-05
	Gymnadenia conopsea	pětiprstka žežulník	O	EN	2023-06

Category	Species	Species [CZ]	Czech law protection	Czech red listing	Last sighting
	<i>Gymnadenia densiflora</i>	pětiprstka hustokvětá	KO	EN	2014-06
	<i>Iris graminea</i>	kosatec trávovitý	SO	VU	2020-05
	<i>Iris pumila</i>	kosatec nízký	SO	VU	2012-04
	<i>Iris sibirica</i>	kosatec sibiřský	SO	VU	2020-09
	<i>Lilium martagon</i>	lilie zlatohlavá	O		2008-06
	<i>Linum hirsutum</i>	len chlupatý	KO	EN	2011-07
	<i>Linum tenuifolium</i>	len tenkolistý	O	NT	2011-07
	<i>Melittis melissophyllum</i>	medovník meduňkolistý	O		2020-09
	<i>Ophrys apifera</i>	tořič včelonosný	KO	EN	2020-09
	<i>Orchis militaris</i>	vstavač vojenský	SO	EN	2023-05
	<i>Platanthera bifolia</i>	vemeník dvoulistý	O	VU	2008-06
	<i>Pulsatilla grandis</i>	koniklec velkokvětý	SO	VU	2023-04
Reptiles	<i>Lacerta agilis</i>	ještěrka obecná	SO	VU	2022-08

Czech law protection abbreviations:

KO - Kriticky ohrožený - Critically Endangered

SO - Silně ohrožený - Strongly Endangered

O – Ohrožený – Endangered

Czech red list abbreviations:

CR – Critically Endangered

EN – Endangered

VU – Vulnerable

NT – Near Threatened

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More information about the project can be found at co2-spicer.geology.cz.

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